

GreenDIGIT

Greener Future Digital Research Infrastructures

Deliverable D5.2 Energy Measurement and Impact Assessment Framework and Methodology and Developer Tooling

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Executive Summary

As Digital Research Infrastructures (DRIs) expand in scale and complexity, their environmental impact has become increasingly significant. While DRIs are essential to the advancement of modern science, they also consume large amounts of energy, generating substantial emissions, and depend on resource-intensive hardware and data services. In this context, there is growing pressure on research institutions and service providers to align their operations with European sustainability regulations and long-term climate goals.

The GreenDIGIT project's Deliverable D5.2 addresses this challenge by focusing on the usage phase of DRIs, with particular attention to how the environmental impact of experimental research conducted within these infrastructures can be quantified and reduced. The deliverable proposes methods and tools targeted to users of DRIs, to support the assessment and mitigation of environmental impacts caused by their experiments.

Key challenges lie in performing lifecycle assessments of experiments. In accordance with Lifecycle Analysis (LCA) methodology and ISO 14000, these include accounting for both direct impacts (such as energy consumption during execution) and indirect impacts (such as the embodied impacts of the underlying infrastructure). While infrastructure operators may have access to relevant data, it is often not accessible to users or structured in a way that supports comprehensive LCA.

To address these gaps, this report presents methodological frameworks and practical tools for users of DRIs. It introduces a user-accessible database that details the environmental footprint of research infrastructure. In addition, it offers a Jupyter plugin for sustainability monitoring and prediction, to raise developers' awareness for the impact of their experiments.

The report also proposes a metadata specification that enables the sharing of end-to-end energy consumption and environmental impact of complex experiments, such as IoT projects, as open data. To support practical adoption and ensure a high technology readiness level, the deliverable includes both technical specifications and prototype implementations of these tools.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
CIM	Common Information Model
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DRI	Digital Research Infrastructure
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
IoT	Internet of Things
LCA	Lifecycle Analysis
LCA-RI	Lifecycle Analysis of Research Infrastructure
LCA-ER	Lifecycle of an Experiment
LCI	Lifecycle Inventory
LCIA	Lifecycle Impact Assessment
NIC	Network Interface Card
NLP	Natural Language Processing
PoE	Powered over Ethernet
PUE	Power Usage Effectiveness
RExRO	Reproducible Experimental Research Object
RI	Research Infrastructure
RILM	Research Infrastructure Lifecycle Model
RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
VM	Virtual Machine
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
VRI	Virtual Research Infrastructure
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

Modern digital Research Infrastructures (RIs) are undergoing a paradigm shift, driven by the dual imperatives of increased scientific reproducibility and environmental sustainability. As scientific workflows grow more complex and data-intensive, the ability to measure and manage the environmental impact of experiments—particularly their energy consumption and carbon footprint—has become essential.

Experimental research introduces additional factors of research or testbed planning, setup/deployment and run to collect/obtain experimental data under a controlled experimental environment.

Developers and researchers require tools that not only enable high-performance and reproducible science and specifically reproducible experimental research but also provide clear insight into the energy and environmental impact associated with their research lifecycle.

This report responds to this challenge by designing an energy measurement and environmental impact assessment framework, supported by developer tools that integrate directly into experimental research environments. Building on the architectural vision presented in the project Deliverable D4.2 “Architecture Definition, Lifecycle Model and Requirements Specification for Sustainable RI” [1], this report advances the GreenDIGIT objective of embedding sustainability across the full lifecycle of digital research infrastructures. The proposed Virtual Research Environment (VRE) and research tools are based on the solution introduced in D4.2, a modular reference architecture and lifecycle model that are used as a basis for supporting/enabling energy-aware orchestration, infrastructure observability, and the integration of sustainability metrics into scientific workflows. D5.2 translates these architectural and strategic principles into a practical, measurable instrumentation layer—one that directly enables energy tracking, environmental impact, and sustainability-aware design within reproducible experimental workflows.

The developer tools and methodologies presented in this deliverable aim to empower researchers to make environmentally conscious decisions throughout the design, execution, and iteration of scientific experiments. These tools are developed as lightweight plugins and extensions to common platforms such as Jupyter and testbed orchestration environments, enabling seamless integration into existing scientific workflows. Additional instrumentation at both the server and client levels - leveraging testbed systems and Internet of Things (IoT) based power measurement from Greenspector, provides end-to-end visibility into energy consumption across the entire experimental infrastructure.

An important development of WP5, and Task T5.2 in particular, is to define the information model and methodological framework necessary for assessing environmental impact at experiment-level granularity. This includes alignment with internationally recognised sustainability standards such as ISO 14040/14044 (Lifecycle Assessment) and the emerging ESRS E1 reporting requirements on energy consumption and Greenhouse gas emissions. The proposed approach links the lifecycle of

scientific experiments with the lifecycle of the underlying research infrastructure, allowing energy and carbon metrics to be contextualised, standardised, and reused across projects and institutions.

In line with the D4.2 Shared Responsibility Model for Sustainability, D5.2 clarifies how researchers, developers, and infrastructure operators can contribute to sustainability goals. Developers are provided with tools to embed energy awareness into applications and services; researchers receive feedback and recommendations to design low-impact experiments; infrastructure operators gain the ability to trace resource-level usage to carbon outcomes. Together, this forms the basis for shared, measurable, and accountable sustainability practices across the research ecosystem.

The deliverable aligns with the development in the partner SLICES-RI on the experimental research reproducibility framework, described in detail in Deliverable D5.1 and introduces the Reproducible Experimental Research Object (RExRO) as an extension of the RO-Crate format. RExRO formalises the inclusion of environmental impact data, such as energy used, emissions generated, hardware profiles, and geolocation, within the digital packaging of experimental workflows and research artefacts. This paves the way for experiments to be not only reproducible, but also environmentally traceable and auditable.

Deliverable D5.2 also provides the basis for implementing the monitoring and metrics infrastructure integrated into VRE and researcher tools. D5.2 defines the architecture, methodology, and prototypes for energy measurement and impact assessment to enable a comprehensive and transparent view of environmental performance across all infrastructure components controlled by the researcher.

In summary, this report D5.2 provides the framework, instrumentation design, and methodological foundation necessary to support environmentally sustainable and reproducible scientific experimentation. By operationalising the sustainability principles defined by the GreenDIGIT architecture and delivering toolchains that bring energy and emissions data into the daily practice of researchers and developers, this deliverable represents a crucial step toward measurable and actionable environmental responsibility in scientific research.

The deliverable is organised in the following way. Chapter 2 introduces the existing approaches in environmental impact assessment, and existing tools that support conducting such assessments, and their limitations. Chapter 3 proposes novel methodological approaches for lifecycle analysis of experiments and the tools needed to conduct this assessment. Chapters 4, 5, and 6 introduce the functional specification of tools, including sharing metrics between operators and users of RI, monitoring and predicting the energy consumption of experimental research, and analysing and sharing the environmental impact of experiments as open data. Chapter 7 provides technical specifications and existing prototypes of such tools. Finally, Chapter 8 concludes the deliverable with perspectives for future work packages of GreenDIGIT.

2 Reproducible Research and Environmental Impact Awareness—Existing Practices and Solutions

The purpose of task T5.2 is to provide tools to developers, i.e. users of RIs, to assist them in assessing the environmental impact of their experiments running on said RIs. While assessing the environmental impact of an experiment is novel, this goal integrates in a wider context of existing works regarding sustainability and energy consumption.

Existing works include international standards, research and industrial monitoring tools, as well as methodological contributions from other GreenDIGIT Work Packages (WPs). The tools introduced in this document must integrate with and iterate on such existing works, while tackling their limitations in the specific context of experiments executed on RIs.

2.1 Lifecycle Assessment Methodologies and Practices—Analysis

Lifecycle Analysis (LCA), also known as Lifecycle Assessment, is a systematic approach to assess the environmental impact of a product, service, or system throughout its entire lifecycle, from raw material extraction to end-of-life disposal [2]. The ISO 14040 [3] and ISO 14044 [4] standards provide a framework for conducting LCA. LCA is widely used to measure and reduce environmental footprints and is a core principle in EU sustainability regulations (e.g., CSRD, ESPR, and EED). Practical aspects of LCA use are supported by multiple guidelines both EC Green Business Initiatives [5] and other initiatives [6].

2.1.1 LCA and ISO14040/ISO14044 Recommendations for Energy and Environmental Impact Assessment

The ISO 14040 (Principles and Frameworks)/ISO 14044 (Requirements and Guidelines) standards address environmental sustainability through Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), which is a structured methodological approach that evaluates the environmental impacts associated with all stages of a product or service lifecycle from raw material extraction through production, distribution, use, recycling, and disposal, i.e. the end-of-life of the product or service.

Although LCA and ISO 14040/ISO 14044 are not directly designed for ICT and digital RIs, their systematic methodology can be used for evaluating the environmental aspects and impacts associated with different RI Lifecycle Model stages, as was done in Chapter 5. Research Infrastructure Lifecycle Model (RILM) of GreenDIGIT Deliverable D4.2.

Figure 1 illustrates the structure of the LCA methodology, containing four main phases described in ISO 14040, while ISO 14044 provides valuable guidelines for Lifecycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) phase together with identified impact factors and recommended metrics.

Figure 1: LCA Phases according to ISO 14040/ISO 14044.

The ISO 14040/ISO 14044 standards define the LCA framework with four main phases:

Phase 1: Goal & Scope Definition

Objective: Define what the LCA aims to measure.

Key aspects for DRIs:

- Assess environmental impacts of HPC, AI clusters, 5G testbeds, and networking infrastructure.
- Define system boundaries (e.g., individual servers, full data centres, IoT sensors).
- Identify environmental categories: carbon footprint, energy efficiency, e-waste generation, water use.

Phase 2: Lifecycle Inventory (LCI)

Objective: Collect data on resource inputs and environmental outputs throughout the lifecycle.

Key data points for DRIs:

- Raw materials & production – Rare earth metals in processors, server chassis materials.
- Operation & energy use – Power consumption, cooling requirements (Power Usage Effectiveness, Carbon Usage Effectiveness, Water Usage Effectiveness).

- Networking infrastructure – Bandwidth and data transmission energy consumption.
- End-of-life disposal – E-waste generation, refurbishment, or recycling rates (WEEE compliance).

Example: Federated AI research testbed LCA would track GPU power usage, cooling energy, carbon emissions, and disposal of outdated AI accelerators.

Phase 3: Lifecycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

Objective: Evaluate the environmental impact categories using collected data.

Key environmental indicators for DRIs that GreenDIGIT selected to use:

Environmental impact category	Environmental impact indicator
Global Warming Potential (GWP) / Climate Change (CC)	Kg CO ₂ eq
Cumulative Energy Demand (CED)	Joule [J] of primary energy demand
Waste of Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE)	Total electrical and electronic waste (kg)

Example: A 5G testbed LCA would measure energy efficiency of radio units, fiber optics carbon footprint, and lifecycle emissions of 5G equipment.

Phase 4: Interpretation & Sustainability Optimisation

Objective: Identify improvements and sustainability strategies.

Key improvement areas for DRIs:

- Optimise ML model training energy efficiency to reduce CO₂ footprint.
- Use modular servers & upgradable networking devices to extend hardware lifespan.
- Implement circular economy by refurbishing and reusing testbed hardware.
- Reduce cooling energy demand with liquid cooling and free cooling systems.
- Shift to renewable energy sources for research computing clusters.

Example: After analysing an IoT testbed's LCA, researchers might reduce emissions by deploying low-power edge computing nodes instead of cloud-heavy architectures.

2.1.2 Applying LCA for RI Sustainability Assessment

While Lifecycle Assessment (LCA) is a well-established method for evaluating environmental impacts, applying it to RIs, like data centres and networked platforms, presents unique challenges.

LCA was originally designed for physical products, not complex, service-based infrastructures. As a result, it struggles to fully capture the environmental footprint of distributed, evolving systems like RIs. One major issue is data availability and quality: infrastructure-wide data is often incomplete, inconsistent, or fragmented, leading to unreliable results. Regional differences in regulations, energy mixes, and practices further complicate comparisons across sites.

LCAs are also resource- and time-intensive, often requiring months of expert effort, but may still miss key lifecycle aspects. The selection of impact categories (e.g., greenhouse gas emissions, water usage, eco-toxicity) is often subjective, and traditional LCA methods tend to overlook social and economic dimensions, such as labour conditions or regional benefits.

Other limitations include difficulties in defining a consistent functional unit for digital services, a lack of temporal and spatial sensitivity (e.g., seasonal energy variations), and high uncertainty in the end-of-life phase, especially given the fast pace of technological obsolescence.

In short, while LCA remains a valuable tool, using it effectively for RIs requires adaptation. The unique characteristics of digital RIs demand new approaches, better data models, and frameworks that reflect the service-based, distributed, and dynamic nature of these systems—while still adhering to the core principles of environmental responsibility and transparency.

2.2 Using LCA methodology for Experiment Lifecycle Impact Assessment

The experiment and scientific workflow execution are performed during the (pre-)operational stage of RI designed for these specific types of experiments. While we can assess the energy consumption and corresponding environmental impact of a given experiment performed on a RI, the full environmental impact of the experiment should also include the embodied impact of the energy and resources (including experiment instruments, hardware, building and construction, software, and other factors contributed/used for RI creation¹). All these factors are inventoried and analysed in the LCA assessment process.

The LCA of an experiment relies on an inventory of data that can only be monitored by the RI operators. In particular, the energy consumption of the different resources used over the different steps of a given experiment, but also the electricity mix used by such resources.

Therefore, the tools proposed in Task T5.2 should support the inclusion of the implied RI impact (as derived from the total RI impact assessment based on LCA process, LCI, LCIA and outcome analysis. The next section proposes the methodology for assessing the implied impact of RI on the experiment

¹ Implied environmental impact of the equipment, hardware, software and data recycling during the RI termination stage may be fully included in the implied hardware impact as a part of its manufacturing process according to ESPR (Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation) via Digital Product Passport [26].

execution, also applied to different experiment lifecycle stages that typically include the experiment development, deployment, execution, data collection, and analysis of results.

2.3 Challenges of Environmental Impact Assessment in Reproducible Research

To assess the environmental impact of a given experiment following an LCA approach, ISO 14040/ISO 14044 defines three steps: defining the scope, conducting the LCI, conducting the LCIA, and interpreting the results. In the specific context of experiments, defining the scope, conducting the LCIA, and interpreting the results are subjective decisions by the person conducting the LCA.

The core issues of performing an LCA lies in the ability to conduct the LCI, i.e., collecting the data used as input to model the environmental impacts. Such data include direct emissions of the DRI, e.g., fossil-fuel-powered backup power supplies of data centres in scope 1, the amount of electricity used and its environmental impact in a scope 2, and the lifecycle impact of goods and services used by the DRI in a scope 3. This section presents the existing tools to collect such data, and their limitations.

2.3.1 Energy measuring in standard infrastructures

Energy efficiency of software has long been a critical concern, driven by the increasing demand for computational power, the associated rise in energy consumption, and the environmental impact of producing such energy. To address this challenge, a wide range of tools, both software and hardware-based, have been developed over the years, to help collecting energy metrics of software systems.

2.3.1.1 *Hardware probes*

Energy measurement capabilities are often designed for RI operators, rather than RI users. RI operators can rely on hardware probes, which are physical watt meters placed between a system to monitor and its power supply. Such probes can be installed as discrete watt meters on each individual server or integrated to the Power Distribution Units (PDUs) of server racks. For devices Powered over Ethernet (PoE), some network switches can provide the energy consumption of each individual network port.

Such solutions are designed for large scale deployment, such as data centres, and support the centralisation of energy metrics over network. Such metrics can then be made accessible to RI operators and users via Application Programming Interface (API) or direct access to energy databases. For instance, such system is implemented by Kwollect on the computer grid Grid'5000².

As physical objects, their deployment is a design decision of the RI operator, and retrofitting such probes into existing RIs may be particularly costly. This disconnect becomes particularly problematic

² <https://gitlab.inria.fr/grid5000/kwollect>

when considering the growing need for reproducible research. Reproducibility not only demands that results can be technically recreated, but also that the environmental impact of computational experiments is traceable and comparable. Without structured access to energy data that is linked to experiment metadata (e.g., configurations, scripts, resource usage), it becomes nearly impossible to evaluate or reproduce the energy footprint of an experiment across testbeds or over time. Bridging this gap requires tooling that embeds energy measurement into the reproducibility workflow and preserves it as part of the experimental artifact.

2.3.1.2 *Software probes*

Software probes are software components that report the energy consumption of a device by reading system metrics from the operating system.

Software probes such as Scaphandre³, PowerAPI [7], or PowerJoular [8] allow for monitoring the energy consumption of bare-metal servers, and to estimate the energy consumption of each process or virtual machines running on such servers. Similarly, Kepler [9] can be used to monitor containerised solutions, exclusively in infrastructures relying on the Kubernetes orchestration system. Such tools are monitoring solutions and export the energy readings to different formats, such as CSV files or Prometheus databases.

The energy consumption of a device can also be accessed programmatically with dependencies such as PyJoule⁴ or JJoules⁵, respectively in Python and Java. Such tools allow for measuring the energy cost of executing a snippet of code by essentially reading the RAPL registers of the device. They are more relevant for micro-benchmarking or small-scale experiments than wider monitoring. While such solutions are mainly designed to monitor the energy consumption of server's CPU, GPUs can also be monitored. Nvidia provides an interface, Nvidia-smi⁶, to collect metrics from Nvidia GPUs, including power usage.

Software probes are easier to deploy and use than hardware probes, but such probes tend to share the same limitations: they extensively rely on RAPL and internal modelling, both of which potentially inducing low accuracy or low precision. In addition, they focus on a single component, the CPU or the GPU, and may thus miss the energy consumption of other components, such as controllers on the motherboard, networking, storage, or even cooling solutions.

2.3.2 Energy measure in heterogeneous infrastructures (IoT)

Greenspector experience with LCA of industrial IoT projects highlights that such projects are a worst-case scenario with regard to energy monitoring, environmental data collection, and impact assessment. Energy monitoring in IoT infrastructures is challenging due to the heterogeneity of hardware: devices can be powered over the power grid, over Ethernet, proprietary wired systems, or

³ <https://github.com/hubblo-org/scaphandre>

⁴ <https://pypi.org/project/pyJoules/>

⁵ <https://github.com/powerapi-ng/j-joules>

⁶ <https://docs.nvidia.com/deploy/nvidia-smi/index.html>

batteries. This diversity in hardware and powering system can exist within a single infrastructure. For instance, a single IoT infrastructure can contain different types of sensors in its sensor network, different controllers in its controller system, a large networking infrastructure including both wired and wireless communication, far edge and near edge layers, while also relying on cloud infrastructures.

Setting up an end-to-end energy monitoring system is thus a challenge even within the testing stage of a given project. Once the end-to-end energy monitoring system is set up, a large amount of data is collected due to the number of devices involved. Analysing such data is an additional challenge, in particular when investigating the most energy efficient architecture for the IoT infrastructure. Such an assessment implies comparing the energy consumption of different scenarios at different granularity: individual devices, groups of devices in each layer (e.g., sensors, networking, far edge...), and the overall consumption of the system. Without a standardised way to organise, share, and analyse such data, end-to-end energy measurement in IoT infrastructure remains an open issue.

2.3.3 From Energy to Environmental impact

RIs such as cloud data centres, high-performance computing clusters, and IoT testbeds are the backbone of modern scientific and industrial progress [10]. These systems continuously generate operational data such as processor usage, memory consumption, power utilisation, cooling status, and environmental telemetry, that is critical not only for monitoring and optimisation but also for assessing their energy usage and environmental impacts. However, the formats, semantics, and structures of these telemetry metrics differ across infrastructures, vendors, and tooling ecosystems. This heterogeneity poses a significant challenge to researchers, sustainability officers, and infrastructure federators who need to compare, reproduce, or assess digital workloads in a harmonised way [11].

The transformation of these RIs into sustainable, interoperable, and federated environments requires unified mechanisms to collect, interpret, and reuse system-level telemetry. These environments generate extensive metrics across domains like performance, energy usage, environmental impact, and resource utilisation. Yet the absence of standardised data models impedes cross-infrastructure understanding and reproducibility. Each DRI records data in siloed formats, with divergent semantics, making large-scale optimisation and policy alignment nearly impossible.

Despite the proliferation of observability platforms such as Prometheus⁷, Scaphandre⁸, OpenTelemetry⁹, InfluxDB¹⁰, and Grafana¹¹, the existing ecosystem of tools falls short in addressing

⁷ <https://prometheus.io/>

⁸ <https://github.com/hubblo-org/scaphandre>

⁹ <https://opentelemetry.io/>

¹⁰ <https://www.influxdata.com/>

¹¹ <https://grafana.com/>

the semantic and interoperability challenges that a Common Information Model (CIM) seeks to resolve. Most tools are optimised for internal observability within a single domain or vendor stack, relying on non-standard metric names, flat schemas, and incompatible aggregation mechanisms. There is no unified approach to representing, discovering, or aligning metrics across infrastructures, making it difficult to implement federated dashboards, sustainability KPIs, or reproducibility-aware workflows. While some platforms support metadata tagging, they rarely incorporate formal ontologies or namespace structures aligned with ISO/IEC 23053:2021 standard [12] or JRC report on Energy-efficient cloud and edge computing [13].

From a scientific standpoint, the integration between telemetry metrics and research metadata remains rudimentary. Tools such as RO-Crate, DataCite¹², or FAIR¹³ Digital Objects support structured metadata for datasets and software, but not for dynamic system metrics. Meanwhile, ontology-driven approaches to infrastructure modelling (e.g., SAREF [14], SSN [15], SEAS¹⁴,) are often domain-specific and lack integration with operational monitoring pipelines [16]. There is a research gap in bridging these communities, i.e. combining the robustness of metric classification with the semantic depth of research metadata standards. Moreover, the absence of automated, self-updated classification engines limits the scalability of current methods.

¹² <https://schema.datacite.org/>

¹³ <https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/FAIR-Metrics-TF-ToR.pdf>

¹⁴ <https://www.seas-project.eu/>

3 Proposed architecture and requirements for sustainability and energy efficiency of experiments

The previous section introduced tools and methodologies for assessing the energy consumption and environmental impact of a RI, and the challenges of converting RI-level metrics, available to the operator of such RIs, into experiment-level metrics available to users of RIs. This section introduces a framework for conducting such a conversion.

3.1 Environmental Impact of RI, environmental impact of experiments

The approach proposed in WP4 Architecture Framework for DRI Sustainability by Design [1] includes the methodology for estimating the environmental impact of the whole lifecycle of RIs. The proposed architecture framework defines the metrics and monitoring infrastructure to collect energy and embodied environmental impact from RI cloud and data centre resources, Virtual Research Environment/Infrastructure (VRE/VRI) and scientific workflows. While this model relies on different stakeholders (policymakers, technical operators of RIs, experimental researchers, and users) and different stages of the lifecycle, it provides only high-level recommendations targeted to policymakers or operators.

The RILM, defined as a part of the architecture framework, includes six stages: Concept development, Design, Development, Deployment and pre-operation, Operation and evolution, and Decommission. While all these steps can be leveraged to reduce the environmental impact of RIs, researchers and developers and corresponding research tools are used primarily during the Operation stage.

This specificity highlights the methodological difference between the LCA of experiments and the LCA of RI which are created and operated for running a specific type of experiment in a repeatable and reproducible way. The RI lifecycle may span more than ten years, with the Operational stage taking most of that time.

For further discussion and analysis, we will distinguish Research Infrastructure Lifecycle Analysis (further referred to as LCA-RI), and Experiment Lifecycle Analysis (further referred to as LCA-ER).

LCA-RI can be based on existing LCA practices for environmental impact assessment as defined by the standards ISO14040/ISO14044. LCA-RI should include all activities and related impact factors for all RI lifecycle stages. Impact factors are generically different for different types of RIs: for digital RIs, environmental impact is primarily defined by consumed energy, types of used energy and water used for cooling. Other impact factors include the embodied impact of hardware manufacturing and equipment recycling at the end of life.

While the LCA-ER can use the general experiment lifecycle model with assessment of the consumed energy based on the typically available energy monitoring data, in the context of RI operation, LCA-

ER should also include the implied environmental impact based on imputed impact calculated for the experiment duration and equipment and facilities use. Methodology for adding the imputed impact for an individual experiment or a set of experiments is discussed below.

RI users perform experiments that contribute to the environmental impact of the infrastructure, as the energy used by experiments contributes to the energy used by the underlying RIs, while also using shared resources and operational costs and their respective impact. Therefore, the environmental impact of each experiment running on RIs should include the indirect impact of the operation stage of such RIs.

Figure 2 illustrates the relation between RI lifecycle stages and the experiment lifecycle stages. The impact of ER is composed of the direct impacts of experiments, mainly through their energy consumption and the electricity-mix impact. In addition, a share of the impact of the RI unrelated to the experiment is imputed, including the embodied impact of the RI, i.e., impacts caused by its design, manufacturing, decommission, but also including impacts caused by the operation of the RI that is independent of experiment. This impact is related to the mutualised energy consumption of the RI, including for instance cooling and networking, generally modelled by its Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE).

Figure 2: Relationship between LCA-RI and LCA-ER for a RI running two experiments.

The overall impact of an experiment can thus be estimated using the following formula:

$$LCA_{ER_c} = \sum_{r \in R} \left((E_r \times PUE \times I_c) + \frac{LCA_{RI_c}}{K} \times k_r \right)$$

In this equation, the impact of an ER in the impact category c (LCA_{ER_c}) is the sum of impacts of all the resources (R) used by the ER. The direct impact of a given resource (r) is its energy consumption multiplied by the PUE of the RI, to account for the mutualised energy consumption of the RI. This overall energy usage is multiplied by I_c the environmental impact of producing this energy in the impact category c . The embodied impact of the RI in the category c (LCA_{RI_c}) is divided by an imputation key K , e.g., the total run time of all experiments in the RI, to convert the embodied impact of the RI into an impact per unit of usage, e.g., per unit of usage time. This impact per unit of usage is multiplied by k_r the actual usage of the resource r during the experiment.

The challenge in applying such a formula lies in the ability for RI users to access the different parameters: the energy consumption of the resources they use, the PUE of the RI, the impact of producing the energy, the embodied impact of the RI and the imputation key. Collecting such metrics is part of the LCI, i.e., phase 2 of conducting LCA-ER. While such metrics are collected and available to RI operators, they are not immediately available to RI users.

To estimate the environmental impact of their experiment, users need to access the environmental data and environmental monitoring tools of the RIs they use. The purpose of Task 5.2 is to provide tools to bridge the gap between the environmental data collection performed by the operator of RI and the data and information that users need to quantify the environmental impact of experiments.

3.2 Tools for sustainability and energy efficiency of the experimental research reproducibility

To reduce the environmental impact of their experimental research, RI users can leverage several actions:

- (a) **Energy efficiency:** by reducing the amount of energy used by a given experiment, RI users can reduce their direct pressure on energy grids, but also the indirect pressure caused by the mutualised energy usage of the RI, in particular the need for cooling.
- (b) **Carbon aware computing:** by identifying optimal time and location to run a given workload, RI users can reduce the environmental impact of the energy they use, while using the same amount of energy.
- (c) **Computing efficiency:** by reducing the quantity of resources, e.g., computing nodes, used by an experiment, RI users can minimise the pressure on hardware and thus reduce the replacement rate of hardware within a RI, or entire RI themselves.

However, conducting such actions requires a deep understanding of the impact of ER, including anticipating the energy consumption of a given experiment, collecting data regarding the environmental impact of past and current experiments, and analysing such data to iteratively minimise the impact of future ER. This highlights the need to bridge the gap between data available to the operators of RIs, data available to the users of RIs, to enable the prediction, monitoring, analysis, and reuse of sustainability metrics.

To address this challenge, we propose a CIM that provides a standardised and extensible approach to describing, classifying, and accessing system-level metrics. Unlike conventional monitoring systems that focus solely on performance visibility, a CIM should incorporate semantic metadata, align with standardised vocabulary, and support namespace interoperability. This will establish a shared structure and terminology across RIs, enabling automation in metric ingestion, as well as usage and analysis for runtime optimisation by developers.

We develop tooling that integrates infrastructure-level metrics with experiment-level metadata. Using structured experiment descriptions based on RO-Crate, the tooling links energy traces directly to specific experiments, nodes, and time windows - making energy consumption visible and attributable across all phases of the research workflow. The developed tooling addresses these issues through seamless access to measurement data from SNMP-compatible devices, automated metadata integration using RO-Crate, and predictive modelling interfaces embedded in Jupyter notebooks. As a result, energy measurement becomes an important part of research output.

Finally, we propose a metadata model to manage, analyse, and share end-to-end energy and sustainability metrics, built on the previously defined monitoring tools, and defining the specific scope of each measured node, and aggregations rules between such nodes.

4 Common Information Model and Unified Metric Namespace & Mapping for Monitoring Sustainability

This work builds upon the foundational design introduced in the GreenDIGIT Deliverable D4.2, particularly Pillar 4 – Common (interoperable) Information Model (CIM) for Sustainability Metrics and Monitoring [1], which outlined the need for a federated semantic layer to enable sustainability-driven metric exchange across Digital Research Infrastructures (DRIs). The CIM presented here serves as a practical and scalable implementation of that pillar, addressing the architectural, semantic, and interoperability challenges identified in deliverable D4.2 by introducing a concrete model for unified namespace mapping, ingestion automation, and metadata packaging.

4.1 General Overview of CIM

A CIM introduces a standardised and extensible way to describe, classify, and access system-level metrics in federated RIs. Unlike traditional monitoring systems that focus solely on performance visibility, a CIM incorporates *semantic metadata*, *standardised vocabulary alignment*, and *namespace interoperability*. It provides a shared vocabulary and structure across RIs, enabling automation in metric ingestion, alignment with international standards: ISO standards defining KPI ISO 30134-1 [18] and others of group ISO 30134-(2-7)¹⁵, ETSI SAREF - *Smart Applications REference Ontology (SAREF)* [19], *EU Code of Conduct on Data Centre Energy Efficiency (JRC-CoC)* [20], and seamless packaging of performance and energy metadata for reproducibility using technologies like RO-Crate and JSON-LD.

The CIM proposed and designed in this deliverable is the extension of Pillar 4 of the architecture framework given in deliverable D4.2 of the GreenDIGIT project. The proposed CIM is based on standardised namespace mapping, semantic classification, and dynamic ingestion. The approach aligns telemetry from diverse infrastructures to harmonised categories grounded in international standards (ISO/IEC 30134, JRC Code of Conduct, IEEE), enabling advanced federated monitoring, sustainability assessment, and metadata enrichment. This approach not only improves data integration and federation across sites but also advances the goals of energy-aware computing, sustainability transparency, and Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR)-compliant [21] reproducible research.

4.1.1 Importance of CIM for interoperability and integration

The introduction of a CIM is critical for advancing the maturity of sustainability and observability frameworks in federated Research Infrastructures (RIs). By offering a unified vocabulary and schema for describing metrics, the CIM enables consistent interpretation of telemetry data across heterogeneous environments. This becomes especially important in our GreenDIGIT project, where the aggregation of performance, energy, and environmental data from multiple computing sites is

¹⁵ISO/IEC 30134-2 to 30134-7:2017–2022 — *Information technology — Data centres — Key performance indicators*.

necessary for accurate impact assessment and optimisation. The CIM decouples the underlying hardware and monitoring tools from the semantic interpretation layer, making the infrastructure more adaptable to evolving sustainability standards and research workflows.

In addition to its structural benefits, the CIM lays the foundation for reproducibility and accountability in open science. Researchers who consume infrastructure resources need to document their computational context including system-level metrics as part of their experimental metadata. With a CIM in place, telemetry like Prometheus and Scaphandre can be semantically encoded using formats like JSON-LD and RO-Crate [22], ensuring that the metric definitions, provenance, and usage contexts are preserved alongside the scientific outputs. Furthermore, the model facilitates real-time insight into infrastructure behaviour, supports automation of energy-aware decisions, and provides a bridge between IT operations and scientific reproducibility initiatives. Its impact extends beyond monitoring, e.g., CIM is foundational to federated intelligence, standard-aligned assessment, and machine-actionable sustainability reporting.

4.1.2 CIM Structural Design Principles

The CIM structural design should provide/achieve a harmonised, semantically grounded, and standards-aligned system for ingesting, classifying, mapping, and packaging sustainability-related metrics across federated RIs. CIM is not limited to a single metric type or toolset; rather, it is built to abstract and unify heterogeneous inputs, whether structured (JSON, XML, YAML), unstructured (TXT, paragraph text), or real-time telemetry from cloud and data centre APIs. By defining a flexible namespace hierarchy grounded in internationally recognised standards such as ISO/IEC 30134, JRC-Code of Conduct, and ETSI SAREF, it is ensured that all metrics are linked to clear definitions, categories, and subcategories, allowing for automation, validation, and reproducibility across platforms.

CIM structure comprises six tightly synergistic components. First, the ingestion component gathers incoming metrics either through API endpoints or a file-uploader supporting JSON, XML, CSV or plain-text streams. The parsing component splits into two branches: a structured parser handles well-formed payloads, while an unstructured parser extracts metrics from log fragments or free text. Once parsed, every metric moves into the classification engine, where it's tagged with a standard, a category, and a sub-category. At that point, the namespace resolver checks the registry: if a matching JSON-LD schema exists, it's retrieved; if not, the namespace generator creates a new schema (encoding standard, category, sub-category, and metric ID/name) and registers it. These mappings are stored in a relational schema (PostgreSQL¹⁶) for structured querying, while metric values are pushed to a time-series store (InfluxDB¹⁷) for observability and real-time analytics. This multi-component design bridges operational telemetry, sustainability reporting, and scientific reproducibility, as illustrated in Figure 3.

¹⁶<https://www.postgresql.org/>

¹⁷<https://github.com/influxdata/influxdb>

The CIM design addresses the critical need for semantic interoperability in cross-infrastructure sustainability monitoring. While modern monitoring tools like Prometheus, Scaphandre, OpenTelemetry, and proprietary APIs are powerful within isolated systems, they lack semantic alignment between DRIs. As federated research environments become more distributed and energy-conscious, the inability to reconcile metric diversity has emerged as a fundamental barrier to optimisation and reproducibility. Existing tools cannot align telemetry with sustainability standards or represent infrastructure metrics in metadata-rich, machine-readable formats. The proposed CIM introduces an extensible, standard-driven architecture that unifies metric ingestion, classification, storage, and discovery—enabling researchers, operators, and policy makers to speak a common language of metrics regardless of source, format, or locality.

Figure 3: General structural design and overview of CIM workflow.

The CIM model emphasises interoperability, extensibility, and semantic clarity across federated RIs through modular design enabling seamless ingestion from heterogeneous sources. The core revolves around a standard-aligned unified namespace, dynamically generated through an intelligent classifier that ensures all incoming metrics are contextually interpreted, semantically tagged, and stored in normalised form. The model implements a dual-storage stack: PostgreSQL maintains taxonomy mappings while InfluxDB captures time-series observations. Additional features such as debugging interfaces and dynamic mapping synchronisation enhance system maintainability, making it a scalable, production-ready solution for federated sustainability monitoring.

4.2 CIM Component Structure and Functionality

To operationalise the proposed CIM for unified metric namespace mapping, the model has been implemented through a modular structure composed of an interlinked yet decoupled components. Each module is responsible for a distinct stage of the telemetry lifecycle, i.e., from data ingestion and parsing to classification, namespace generation, storage, and semantic packaging.

This model was designed to support extensibility, automation, and standard-aligned interoperability. By separating concerns into functional components, the system can scale horizontally across diverse infrastructure sources and evolve to accommodate new metric types, formats, and semantic standards. The following subsections provide a detailed breakdown of each component's role, logic, and contribution to the overarching goal of building a reproducible, sustainable, and federated monitoring ecosystem.

4.2.1 Ingestion Engine

The ingestion engine is the entry point of the CIM design, responsible for acquiring metric data from diverse sources. It handles multiple ingestion modalities: structured file-based uploads (JSON, XML, YAML, CSV), real-time streaming from public cloud APIs, and unstructured text typically provided by non-technical stakeholders. The engine performs format detection and normalisation to ensure consistency across ingestion pathways, enabling both human-generated documentation and machine-generated telemetry to be parsed without additional tooling.

Internally, the ingestion component initiates parsing through format-specific handlers. For structured data, it performs schema traversal to extract key-value metric pairs and maps them to an interim representation. For unstructured data, it employs Natural Language Processing (NLP) routines to identify candidate metric phrases, values, and units, even if the terms are scattered across prose. It then forwards the raw metric keys and contextual metadata (e.g., source, timestamp, origin) to the classification component. This early normalisation phase enables downstream automation and interoperability.

By supporting multiple data entry methods, the ingestion engine ensures inclusivity and scalability of the CIM. It enables onboarding of new infrastructures without requiring a specific monitoring

framework, lowers adoption barriers for less technical users, and creates a uniform input stream for semantic processing.

4.2.2 Universal Format-Aware Parser and Metric Extractor

The Universal Parser component serves as the ingestion gateway for heterogeneous telemetry sources. It is designed to automatically detect the format of incoming metric files or streams such as JSON, XML, CSV, YAML, or plain text, and apply the appropriate parsing strategy to extract relevant metric key-value pairs. This component is critical for interoperability, as real-world data centres and monitoring systems often expose data in incompatible or undocumented formats.

Once a file or data stream is received, the parser uses Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions (MIME) type detection or content introspection to route the input through specialised handlers (e.g., `json_parser`, `xml_parser`, `csv_loader`, or `unstructured_text_parser`). For each recognised metric, the parser normalises its structure into a consistent dictionary-like object that can then be forwarded to the Semantic Classifier Engine component for semantic categorisation and namespace assignment.

For unstructured formats such as `.txt` or paragraph-style logs, the parser uses lightweight NLP techniques and pattern recognition, i.e. *regular expressions*, *keyword proximity*, *sentence-level tagging*, to infer metric names and values embedded in natural language. This ensures that even non-technical metric submissions such as those from legacy systems or manual reports can also be semantically interpreted and integrated into the unified model.

By abstracting the complexity of source formats, the Universal Parser allows CIM to support real-time ingestion, archival uploads, and cross-system interoperability, regardless of how the data is originally structured.

4.2.3 Hierarchical Namespace and Identifier Design Principles

4.2.3.1 Semantics-based Classifier Engine

The semantic classifier acts as the intelligence component of the CIM model, transforming the heterogeneous landscape of DRIs telemetry into a unified, interoperable framework. It maps incoming raw metric keys that are often unstandardised, ambiguous, or inconsistent, into a well-defined taxonomy grounded in international standards including ISO/IEC 30134, JRC Code of Conduct, and SAREF ontologies. This semantic classification component determines the **standard**, **category**, and **subcategory** for each metric, using a hybrid approach that blends rule-based logic, keyword extraction, and database-assisted inference, serving as the key enabler for transforming raw data into semantically meaningful structures.

4.2.3.2 Namespace Generator

The namespace generator component design follows a modular and hierarchical structure that separates metric categories, types, and contextual application layers to ensure semantic interoperability, traceability, and flexibility across DRIs. This component produces the standardised,

fully qualified unified key for each metric. It constructs namespace based on following hierarchy form. then each unified key is validated to ensure it does not conflict with existing entries and is appended to the metric definition table and mapping registry. The namespace is not just a naming convention, i.e. it is a formal semantic handle that encapsulates the origin, type, and contextual meaning of the metric.

unified keys => <standard>.<category>.<subcategory>.<metric_ID/Name>

unified ID (URI) => gd-metric:<category>/<site>/<resource>/<timestamp>

Unified keys are used internally for querying, indexing, and readability. Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) are globally unique identifiers for referencing, provenance, and integration. For example, a metric indicating power usage might be mapped as **iso.energy.power.total**, while disk input/output operations could become **jrc.storage.disk.read_iops**.

This hierarchical structure is used in the later phase for storage in relational and time-series databases. Further from this namespace structure, unique identifier URI or Qnames are developed that employs the proposed URI pattern <http://greendigit.eu/ns/metrics/> with established customised prefix **gd-metric:** for GreenDIGIT-defined metrics. Some of the known prefix and namespace identifiers are given in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Proposed and know namespace prefix and identifier

Prefix	Suggested URIs	Descriptions
gd-metric:	http://greendigit.eu/ns/metrics/	Custom developed core namespace for GreenDIGIT-defined metrics
iso30134:	http://iso.org/iso30134/	Standardised for Datacenter’s Energy and Water KPIs
saref:	https://w3id.org/saref	ETSI Smart Appliance REF ontology (energy)
dcat:	http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat	Dataset cataloguing metadata
schema:	http://schema.org/	General digital object metadata

At runtime, the classifier consults a centralised relational database that houses predefined metric keywords, synonyms, and historical mappings organised into five primary category-based sub-namespaces: **energy metrics** (**gd-metric:energy/**), **efficiency metrics** (**gd-metric:efficiency/**), **carbon emission metrics** (**gd-metric:carbon/**), **water usage metrics** (**gd-metric:water/**), and **resource utilisation metrics** (**gd-metric:resource/**).

When a metric such as "mem_used" or "memory.usage" is encountered, the classifier matches it against known entries and assigns it to the appropriate taxonomy path for instance, mapping memory-related metrics to performance → memory → usage within the resource utilisation category. The system employs contextual identifiers for each of the metric from the DRI that include machine-readable URI (QNames) which is composed of components such as site ID, resource ID, and timestamps, generating URIs like `gd-metric:energy/vm/siteA/vm123/2025-05-28T15:00Z`. Each contextual URI ensures global uniqueness and persistent identification. Each of them also supports JSON-LD for integration with tools like RO-Crate packaging. It also supports existing identifiers wherever applicable e.g., UUIDs for VMs/tasks. Some examples from these five primary categories with the designed GreenDIGIT namespace prefix and URI are given in Appendix A.

4.2.3.3 Dynamic Classification and Extensibility

If a new or unknown metric appears, the classifier leverages pattern recognition and contextual NLP to make a best-effort classification, flags the entry, and records it for further refinement. This dynamic extensibility allows the system to evolve as new metrics emerge while maintaining alignment with the three GreenDIGIT monitoring levels, similar to the prototype of **EcoJupyter** developed in D5.1: **L1** (experiment/workflow level mapped to `gd-metric:energy/experiment/`), **L2** (site selection mapped to `gd-metric:carbon/site/`), and **L3** (resource/node management mapped to `gd-metric:resource/node/`).

4.2.3.4 Metrics Taxonomy

The classification system encompasses comprehensive metrics definitions across all categories. **Energy metrics** include total energy consumed (`gd-metric:energy/totalEnergy`), energy per task (`gd-metric:energy/energyPerTask`), and CPU power draw measurements. **Efficiency metrics** incorporate standardised indicators like Power Usage Effectiveness (`iso30134:PUE`), Cooling Efficiency Ratio (`gd-metric:efficiency/CER`), and PowerScore23 for normalised CPU energy efficiency. **Carbon emission metrics** track CO₂ equivalent emissions through Carbon Usage Effectiveness (`iso30134:CUE`), carbon intensity factors, and job-specific carbon footprints. **Water usage metrics** monitor consumption through Water Usage Effectiveness (`iso30134:WUE`) and water reuse ratios, while **resource utilisation metrics** measure CPU utilisation, memory load, I/O throughput, and active-idle node ratios.

4.2.3.5 Semantic Output and Integration

The classifier's output is a **semantic triple**: (`category`, `subcategory`, `short_key`), which is passed to the namespace generator to create persistent and shareable identifiers compatible with JSON-LD formatting and RO-Crate packaging. Each metric URI ensures global uniqueness through PID services integration, supports JSON-LD for tool integration, and respects existing identifiers such as UUIDs for VMs and tasks. This classification layer ensures consistency across infrastructures, makes metrics discoverable across domains, and forms the semantic backbone of the CIM while enabling federated monitoring, sustainability assessment, and metadata enrichment through advanced linked data technologies.

To ensure compliance with EU regulations including ESPR, CSRD/ESRS, EED, and WEEE, the taxonomy incorporates additional metrics such as Energy Reuse Factor (ERF), renewable energy factors, Scope 1/2/3 emissions tracking, and lifecycle assessment scores. The system supports extensibility through additional categories like **lifecycle metrics** (`gd-metric:lifecycle/`) and **data movement metrics** (`gd-metric:data/`) to accommodate emerging sustainability requirements and circular economy indicators.

4.2.4 Relational and Time-series Storage

Storage in the CIM model is decoupled into two complementary layers: a **relational database (PostgreSQL)** and a **time-series database (InfluxDB)**. Each serves a specific purpose. The relational store captures the static schema, i.e. ontologies, taxonomy trees, mapping registries, metric definitions, and provenance metadata, as shown Figure 4. It enables high-performance querying of metric metadata, classification rules, and semantic relationships. Tables such as `standards`, `categories`, `metric_keywords`, and `metric_definitions` are linked through primary-foreign key constraints, allowing deep analytical operations.

Figure 4: Metric collection and storage via PostgreSQL with proposed namespace structure.

The time-series database, on the other hand, stores the real-time or historical values of the metrics themselves. Each observation includes a timestamp, the unified key, and the value. This enables infrastructure operators and researchers to track performance and sustainability over time, generate visualisations, and support predictive modelling. The two databases are synchronised through the

ingestion flow: every new unified key written to InfluxDB is first validated and registered in PostgreSQL. This dual-database architecture enables both structural consistency (via SQL) and performance tracking (via Influx), ensuring that the system is analytically powerful and semantically robust.

4.2.5 Mapping Registry Sync with JSON Integration

The mapping registry module maintains a `metric_mapping.json` file that serves as a human-readable and machine-queryable dictionary of raw-to-unified mappings. This file mirrors the state of the metric definitions table in PostgreSQL and is automatically updated whenever a new metric is classified and registered. Each entry contains the `unified_key`, the source key(s), and relevant tags.

```
{
  "iso.energy.power.total": {
    "sources": ["power_usage", "dc.power"],
    "tags": ["energy", "power", "iso"]
  }
}
```

The mapping registry acts as a lightweight external interface for tools that cannot directly access the database. It enables downstream services such as dashboards, report generators, or visualisation layers to retrieve meaningful names, search by tags, and display appropriate units. The JSON sync mechanism ensures that this file stays updated with every ingestion operation. Through this registry, the CIM architecture becomes transparent, extensible, and integrable with other semantic tools like RO-Crate or metadata brokers.

4.3 Metadata Schema Generation with JSON-LD

The metadata schema in the proposed CIM is designed to capture not just the value of a metric, but its context, semantics, and lineage. This schema encodes details such as the source infrastructure, the origin of the metric (file/API), classification trail (how the raw key was translated to its unified form), associated standards, units, and timestamps. The metadata schema also integrates mappings between raw keys and standardised namespace identifiers, ensuring that data reuse and sharing are always tied to an unambiguous semantic definition. This structured schema forms the backbone of machine-actionable documentation, enabling reproducibility, traceability, and federated interpretation of the data.

To ensure interoperability and adherence to FAIR principles, the CIM encodes its metadata schema in JSON-LD (JSON for Linked Data). JSON-LD allows us to annotate the telemetry records with linked data identifiers that connect them to widely recognised vocabularies and ontologies, such as `iso30134:`, `saref:`, or `jrc:`. But for the GreenDIGIT project, it has been linked to the proposed developed `gd-metric`: This makes each metric not just a local label, but a globally understood concept, discoverable via semantic search engines and integrable with external knowledge graphs.

Each record produced through ingestion can be packaged as a self-contained JSON-LD object, carrying both its value and its semantic annotations.

The process begins after metric classification and namespace assignment. Once a unified key is generated, the CIM queries the relational schema to retrieve its full semantic profile, i.e. standard origin, category path, unit, and definition. These elements are then assembled into a metadata block conforming to JSON-LD syntax. For instance, a power usage metric might be encoded with **@context** definitions pointing to the ISO ontology, include **@type** as **EnergyConsumption**, and include linked metadata such as **dc:source** (infrastructure name) and **dc:date** (observation time). Additional nested blocks can represent provenance, data quality, and measurement method, making the representation both rich and extensible. This approach ensures that each metric is not only standardised, but also contextualised and machine-readable, directly supporting interoperability, metadata packaging, and scientific reproducibility in federated infrastructures.

An example of JSON-LD with detail of its components for the instance of Power Usage Metrics is given in Appendix B.

4.3.1 Metadata Definition in RO-Crate Using JSON-LD Format

Research Object Crate (RO-Crate) is a community-driven specification that packages digital research artifacts and their associated rich metadata using a **JSON-LD-based standard**. This lightweight structure allows for representing research datasets, workflows, software, and provenance information, while also packaging structured metadata alongside the actual files or links to them. This design promotes interoperability and reproducibility across various platforms and disciplines.

An RO-Crate typically consists of a directory or archive (like a ZIP or TAR file) containing the research files. Crucially, it includes a special **JSON-LD file** named **ro-crate-metadata.json** in the root directory. Optionally, an **ro-crate-preview.html** file can be included to provide human-readable summaries. This structure ensures that machines can easily parse the crate for automation, while humans can understand its contents through visual tools.

To integrate with RO-Crate, each ingested and mapped metric observation is included as an environmental related data entity, with its corresponding JSON-LD metadata embedded or linked in the **ro-crate-metadata.json** file. Each metric can be treated as either:

A **Dataset** if it refers to a structured time series or batch of observations, or

A **File** or **Record** if it originates from a document, ingestion log, or snapshot.

Using RO-Crate for experiment data documenting allows contextual entities such as datacenter profiles, ingestion processes, classifiers used, and even software agents that are to be defined and referenced. This means RO-Crate can describe not only *what metrics were observed*, but *how they were classified, where they came from, when they were generated, and what tools were involved*. As such, a complete RO-Crate package becomes a portable, self-describing object that other

infrastructures or researchers can inspect, rerun, or compare, meeting both **FAIR** and **Open Science** principles.

Each RO-Crate consists of:

- A directory or archive (e.g., ZIP or TAR) containing files.
- A special JSON-LD file named `ro-crate-metadata.json` in the root directory.
- Optionally, a `ro-crate-preview.html` to render human-readable summaries.

This structure allows machines to parse the crate for automation and humans to understand its contents via visual tools. The heart of a RO-Crate is the `ro-crate-metadata.json`, which includes:

- `@graph`: An array of JSON-LD objects describing each file, dataset, person, software, or process involved.
- A `mainEntity`: Pointing to the primary subject of the research.
- Contexts, identifiers, types, and relations (e.g., `wasGeneratedBy`, `usedSoftware`, `producedBy`).

For the CIM, this `@graph` structure specifically incorporates:

- Metric observations, as JSON-LD data entities.
- The ingestion script or API (as `SoftwareApplication`).
- The datacenter (as `Place` or `Organisation`).
- The classifier tool (as `Workflow` or `Agent`).
- The measurement units and standards (as `ConceptScheme` or `OntologyReference`).

These elements are interconnected using properties from schema.org and custom-developed `gd-metric` vocabularies. This comprehensive linking creates a **navigable, extensible, and machine-actionable** package that not only describes the data itself but also the vital **context** of its generation and processing.

4.3.2 Using CIM for Metadata Expression in RO-Crate

CIM design allows every metric whether it is from structured files or real-time ingestion that is to be wrapped in a standardised metadata envelope. As such **Researchers** can understand how a metric was derived, what system it came from, and under what conditions. **Other systems** can verify, reuse, or ingest these metrics with full traceability. **Federated DRIs** can align metric collection strategies through shared ontologies and classifications. **Auditors or sustainability assessors** can validate compliance with energy or performance KPIs through linked provenance.

This means that an institution could share a RO-Crate bundle of its sustainability metrics with another data center, a journal, or an EOSC repository, and it would carry with it the *full semantic context, classification, and provenance* needed to make it meaningful. This also ensures **long-term reuse, transparent evaluation, and replication** of any system-level experiment, making CIM system not just an operational backend but a cornerstone of sustainable, open, and verifiable science.

The proposed structural design of CIM plays a pivotal role in realising the GreenDIGIT vision by providing a semantic foundation for sustainability monitoring across federated DRIs. Its expression for Metadata in RO-Crate packaging ensures that all energy, efficiency, and performance-related telemetry metrics are collected through GreenDIGIT tools and are recorded and understood in a standardised, machine-actionable manner.

Within the GreenDIGIT stack, the CIM will serve as a core interoperability layer, connecting observability tools (e.g., energy probes, Prometheus exporters, cloud APIs) with downstream analytics, reproducibility pipelines, and reporting systems. It will enable the harmonisation of diverse metric sources, support RO-Crate-based reproducibility metadata generation, and assist in cross-infrastructure metric comparison, which is a foundational step toward impact assessment and federated optimisation. By aligning metric classification with international standards (ISO 30134, JRC, IEEE), it ensures that GreenDIGIT's sustainability KPIs are both credible and interoperable with European research policy frameworks.

5 Environmental Impact Metric Assessment in Testbed, Bare-Metal, and Post-5G Infrastructure using Jupyter

The objective of Task 5.2 is to enable researchers to assess the energy impact of their experimental workflows and software artefacts. In the context of increasing demands for sustainability and reproducibility in digital research, this task develops targeted tooling that integrates energy awareness into the everyday practices of experimenters.

Three key capabilities have been developed:

- 1) The system provides evaluations and visualisations of energy behaviour over time based on previously executed experiments. These evaluations help researchers identify energy hotspots and patterns across different workload profiles and across heterogeneous compute resources, including CPU- and GPU-intensive executions.
- 2) The tooling introduces predictive modelling techniques that estimate energy consumption based on experimentally relevant parameters, such as CPU load levels, GPU utilisation levels, and the use of Network Interface Cards (NICs). Separate regression-based energy models are derived for different hardware components, enabling component-aware and node-specific predictions.
- 3) A browser-based prediction interface makes this modelling accessible and interactive, allowing researchers to configure hypothetical experiment setups and compare their energy implications for heterogeneous node configurations, including optional GPU acceleration where available. By making energy feedback available both post hoc (1) and proactively (2, 3), the tooling supports the design of energy-efficient experiments and offers a reproducible baseline for further optimisation and comparison.

The integration of these key components provides the foundation for environmental impact assessments. Specifically, the outputs of this task serve as upstream inputs for Work Package 6, where carbon footprint calculations are carried out based on standardised emissions factors. In doing so, the tooling developed here directly contributes to the GreenDIGIT project's broader aim of enabling energy-aware and reproducible research across infrastructures.

5.1 Functional Components

The architectural design is organised into three main functional components, hardware infrastructure, software applications, and visualisation plugins, all connected via a pluggable interface layer. This modular approach ensures seamless data flow from low-level energy measurement devices through metadata processing applications to high-level visualisation and prediction tools (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Overall Architecture of Experimental Data Collection System.

At the hardware level, the system supports integration with energy measurement devices such as GUDE Expert Power Control units and other SNMP-compatible power distribution solutions. These

allow for continuous monitoring of voltage, current, and power consumption during experiment execution across heterogeneous server configurations, including CPU- and GPU-equipped nodes. The resulting measurement data is enriched with structured metadata conforming to the RO-Crate standard, enabling traceable and machine-readable documentation of experimental setups, including details about node configurations, authorship, and the exact parameters under which measurements were obtained. To support live observability and debugging, the system integrates with Prometheus¹⁸ for metric collection and Grafana¹⁹ for real-time dashboarding. These components provide immediate visual feedback on the electrical behaviour of the infrastructure, making it easier to detect anomalies such as voltage instability or unexpected energy spikes during runtime that may arise from both CPU- and GPU-intensive workloads.

Finally, energy prediction tasks are supported through interactive, Jupyter-based tools. These tools allow researchers to perform statistical analyses, build predictive energy models, and simulate various system configurations to explore the energy implications of different experimental designs by modelling the individual contributions of CPUs, GPUs (where available), and network interfaces. The system is validated on both bare-metal server infrastructures, where full hardware control is available, and next-generation testbed environments such as post-5G platforms, where reproducibility and sustainability are crucial for scalable experimentation.

The presented system architecture builds on the general GreenDIGIT Architecture Framework [1] and implements functionalities of the upper two layers of the Pillar 1 Layered and Modular Architecture for Sustainable Digital Infrastructures, specifically Layer 4 Research Development Environment and Scientific Workflow, and Layer 5 Researcher Tools and Portal, and extends them with the application stack for experiment-level energy measurement and assessment, which provides input to Layer 4. The integration of energy measurement hardware and Prometheus-based metrics collection introduces an important experiment infrastructure observability layer. The use of RO-Crate for structured metadata aligns with the reproducibility and sustainability packaging functionality corresponding to the Pillar 4 (CIM) for Sustainability Metrics and Monitoring, enabling machine-readable descriptions of experimental conditions. The Jupyter-based modelling and visualisation tools, implemented as a part of the Software and Scientific Applications Design Patterns (Pillar 2), allow researchers to simulate, analyse, and reduce the environmental footprint of their experiments.

5.1.1 Test Applications

To validate the developed tooling, a set of controlled test applications was executed on both bare-metal and virtualised testbed environments. These applications were chosen to simulate typical computing and network workloads and to stress different system components, enabling meaningful power measurement and modelling.

The following test scenarios were used:

¹⁸ <https://prometheus.io>

¹⁹ <https://grafana.com>

- **CPU Stress Tests:** synthetic CPU load was generated with defined load levels (25%, 50%, 75%, 100%). These runs were used for power modelling and for evaluating linear vs. polynomial energy models.
- **Network Activity Simulation:** NIC-intensive tasks using the packet generator MoonGen²⁰ were executed to measure and evaluate the power consumption of the network cards.
- **GPU Stress Tests:** controlled GPU workloads were generated using the gpu-burn²¹ benchmark tool, applying reproducible load levels to GPU-equipped nodes. These experiments were used to derive regression-based GPU energy models and to quantify the contribution of accelerator-based computation to overall system power consumption.
- **Idle Baselines:** control experiments with idle nodes were used to measure baseline consumption in Grafana (see Figure 6).

5.2 Main Tooling Components

The Jupyter based tool consists of three main parts. The live energy measurement and monitoring component collects available energy data from available sources. In the second part, experiment metadata is extracted to model the experiment workload and hardware. The third part provides statistical evaluation of collected data.

5.2.1 Live Energy Measurement and Monitoring

An important component of the tooling developed under Task 5.2 is the ability to capture live energy consumption data during the execution of experiments. Accurate and timely access to physical power metrics is essential not only for post-hoc analysis but also for enabling researchers to monitor and adapt ongoing experimental runs with sustainability in mind across both CPU- and GPU-intensive workloads.

The system achieves this by interfacing with established energy measurement infrastructure, including GUDE Expert Power Control²² units and other SNMP²³-compatible power meters. These devices provide real-time access to electrical parameters such as voltage, current, and active power. To ensure portability and integration into existing RI workflows, the system exposes these measurements via Prometheus-compatible exporters. This allows energy metrics to be collected alongside other system telemetry and visualised through Grafana dashboards. In this configuration, researchers gain the ability to observe power behaviour across nodes and time, including the detection of anomalies such as voltage drops, surges, or irregular consumption patterns that might indicate misconfiguration or hardware faults arising from high-load CPU or GPU execution phases.

²⁰ <https://github.com/emmericp/MoonGen>

²¹ <https://github.com/wilicc/gpu-burn>

²² <https://gude-systems.com/produkte/expert-power-control-8025/>

²³ <https://www.snmp.com/protocol/>

metadata in a lightweight JSON-LD²⁵ format. It enables the bundling of structured metadata with the actual research artefacts, such as energy consumption measurements, configuration files, execution scripts, measurement logs, and documentation into a coherent and self-describing digital package.

In the context of this tooling, RO-Crate serves as foundation for the extraction of important metadata of an experiment executed in a testbed. Each experiment is accompanied by a *ro-crate-metadata.json* file, which encodes detailed descriptions of the experiment's components. This includes hardware-specific information (e.g., processor models, memory capacity, type and number of installed GPUs and NICs), software dependencies, execution parameters, as well as the provenance of artefacts used and generated. Crucially, RO-Crate also facilitates author attribution by capturing metadata such as the name of the experiment creator, persistent identifiers (e.g., ORCID²⁶), and institutional affiliations, expressed using standardised schema.org properties like creator, affiliation, and identifier.

By systematically parsing a RO-Crate, the system ensures that measurement data can be contextually enriched without manual input. This not only guarantees reproducibility by preserving the experimental context, but also traceability, by linking results to specific individuals and resources. Moreover, the integration of RO-Crate metadata allows for automatic mapping between measurement data and system configurations, enabling consistent documentation and alignment with broader reproducibility and sustainability standards. This approach supports the long-term goal of making experimental artefacts FAIR and aligns with best practices in open science and energy-aware computing.

On the technical level, the tooling automatically parses node-specific hardware characteristics and experiment parameters. This includes CPU and GPU model information, NIC identifiers, and node names, which are essential for correlating measurement data with the physical infrastructure on which the experiment was conducted. By embedding this metadata directly into the energy analysis pipeline, the system removes the need for manual configuration or annotation, thereby reducing error and increasing reproducibility (see Figure 7).

The tool also extracts authorship metadata, including the names of the experiment author(s), their persistent identifiers such as ORCID, and institutional affiliations. This metadata is essential for ensuring proper attribution, enabling auditability, and linking energy measurement results to individual researchers or teams. It also facilitates integration with publication workflows and sustainability reporting mechanisms (see Figure 8).

Together, these metadata components render experiments traceable (by linking actions to specific individuals and hardware), reproducible (through full description of the runtime environment), and attributable (with assigned authorship). Furthermore, the automatic association of measurement

²⁵ <https://json-ld.org>

²⁶ <https://orcid.org>

data with configuration metadata allows for seamless mapping of energy profiles to specific experimental conditions.

name	fqdn	topology_pdf	CPU	Cores	Threads	Memory	NICs
Node riga	riga.baltikum.net.cit.tum.de	Open PDF	Xeon E31230 @ 3.20GHz	4	8	16 GiB	82576 Gigabit 82576 Gigabit 82579LM Gigabit (Lewisville) 82574L Gigabit
Node vilnius	vilnius.baltikum.net.cit.tum.de	Open PDF	Xeon E31230 @ 3.20GHz	4	8	16 GiB	1350 Gigabit 82579LM Gigabit (Lewisville) 82574L Gigabit

Figure 7: Metadata Extraction of Experiment Nodes from RO-Crate.

Creator Name	ORCID	Contribution (CRediT)	Affiliation Name	Affiliation ROR	Affiliation URL
Kilian Warmuth	ORCID Profile	Software, Methodology	Technical University of Munich	ROR ID	Website
Alice Doe	ORCID Profile	Software	Technical University of Munich	ROR ID	Website
Sepp Meier	ORCID Profile	Validation	University of Applied Sciences Landshut	ROR ID	Website

Figure 8: Author Metadata Extraction from RO-Crate.

5.2.3 Common Statistical Evaluation of Measurements

In order to provide researchers with actionable insights into the energy behaviour of their experiments, the tooling includes automated statistical analysis of the collected measurement data. These statistical evaluations are computed post-experiment and offer a comprehensive understanding of energy consumption patterns across nodes and over time. The notebook computes standard descriptive statistics, including the mean, median, maximum, and minimum values of power consumption for each node and experiment run. Additionally, measures of dispersion such as standard deviation are calculated, and basic outlier detection is performed to identify atypical readings that may indicate transient faults or measurement noise. An example of this common set of statistical evaluations is shown in Figure 9, which illustrates a representative dashboard for statistical evaluation across multiple experiment nodes.

Beyond numerical summaries, the system provides visualisation tools that represent energy data in an accessible and interpretable manner. Temporal plots illustrate energy usage over the duration of the experiment, enabling researchers to correlate load phases with consumption trends. Voltage readings are also visualised, allowing the identification of electrical anomalies or hardware instability. Finally, aggregate energy consumption over the full duration of the experiment is computed and

plotted, typically in watt-hours (Wh), supporting comparisons between experimental setups and configurations.

These statistical outputs form the basis for both exploratory analysis and comparative benchmarking. They are particularly valuable in heterogeneous testbed environments, where understanding per-node variation is critical for reproducibility, optimisation, and sustainability assessment.

	current_mA	voltage_V	power_active_W	energy_counter_Wh
count	1805.000000	1805.000000	1805.000000	1805.000000
mean	546.346814	229.966759	114.977839	2.661496
std	74.807613	1.297705	17.635398	2.151957
min	346.000000	228.000000	66.000000	0.000000
25%	508.000000	229.000000	106.000000	1.000000
50%	531.000000	230.000000	111.000000	2.000000
75%	621.000000	231.000000	133.000000	4.000000
max	651.000000	233.000000	139.000000	8.000000

Figure 9: Common Set of Statistical Evaluations.

5.3 Test Results – Example Measurement and Metrics

In this subsection, example results of the environmental impact assessment tool are described. First, total energy consumption is shown. Then, plots of the collected data are presented.

5.3.1 Total Energy Consumption

To provide a clear overview of resource usage, the system computes and visualises the total corrected energy consumption per node over the full duration of the experiment. As shown in Figure 10, this plot represents the cumulative energy draw in watt-hours (Wh) for each participating node, based on the integrated measurement data. This direct visualisation enables researchers to assess which nodes consumed more energy during the same experimental run and may offer initial indications of relative efficiency, such as whether one node executed the workload more energy-efficiently than another under comparable conditions. It also helps to increase the researchers' awareness regarding the total energy consumed of the experiment.

Figure 10: Total Energy Consumption Chart per Node.

5.3.2 Energy Plots

To further support interpretability and informed decision-making, the tooling provides different visualisations of energy consumption and electrical conditions over time. These visual outputs are also based on the raw measurement data embedded in the RO-Crate, enabling researchers to inspect the temporal behaviour of power and voltage without requiring additional instrumentation or manual processing.

Figure 11 presents the power consumption profiles of two experiment nodes over the course of an experimental run. These time-series plots reveal how power usage evolves in response to workload changes, system transitions, or scripted phases of the experiment. Characteristic patterns, such as sharp increases in power draw, plateaus, or drops, can be identified, supporting both analysis and high-level documentation of experiment energy consumption. Another useful plot as part of our evaluation notebook is shown in Figure 8. It visualises the corresponding voltage trend over time. While generally stable, voltage fluctuations can occur due to infrastructure-level factors or high-load conditions, and they may influence the reliability of power readings. This visualisation helps detect such anomalies and supports quality assurance in power-sensitive experiments.

These temporal plots, derived directly from RO-Crate packaged energy records, enable researchers to diagnose execution phases, detect irregularities, and validate measurement integrity. They are particularly valuable in complex or multi-node experiments, where synchronised insight into node behaviour is essential for reproducibility and result interpretation.

Figure 11: Power Consumption Plot of Experiment (Two Nodes).

Figure 12: Voltage Trend over Time of an Experiment (Two Nodes).

5.4 Energy Modeling and Prediction

To support pre-execution estimation of energy demand, the tooling incorporates a power modelling framework based on empirical measurements and regression techniques. The modelling process focuses on decomposing total server power into a baseline component and additive contributions from GPUs, CPU cores and NICs. The central formulation used in this approach is:

$$P_{server} = P_{base} + \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \cdot P_{core,i} + \sum_{j=1}^k \lambda_j \cdot P_{nic,j} + \sum_{l=1}^m \lambda_l \cdot P_{gpu,l}$$

In this equation, P_{server} denotes the real-world measured idle or baseline power of the node, $P_{core,i}$ is the power contribution of each CPU core, to be multiplied by their respective utilisation level, and $P_{nic,j}$ represents the power usage of the NIC, weighted by its activity state. $P_{gpu,l}$ denotes the power contribution of an individual GPU, scaled by its utilisation level, where applicable. This additive model enables the isolation of component-wise energy profiles under realistic load conditions.

Model construction proceeds through structured measurement experiments, where energy usage is recorded under controlled utilisation of CPU cores and, where available, controlled GPU workloads. From this data, both linear regression models and polynomial models are fitted. The linear model assumes a proportional relationship between the number of active cores and power consumption, while the polynomial model captures non-linear effects such as power plateaus, inefficiencies, or thermal impacts under high utilisation.

Model quality is evaluated by comparing predicted values to ground truth measurements using residual analysis and error metrics such as mean absolute error. This evaluation helps determine whether the additional complexity of non-linear models is justified for a given system. All models are exported in structured JSON format (*node_model.json*) to support reproducibility. These stored models can be reloaded for use in subsequent prediction tasks without requiring retraining, ensuring consistency across runs and users. This approach enables energy-aware planning and benchmarking, even when measurements are not available in advance. This format captures the model parameters, fitted coefficients, and baseline power values, allowing the models to be reloaded and applied in future prediction tasks without the need for retraining. This capability ensures consistency across experiments, users, and infrastructures, enabling reliable energy estimation even when real-time measurements are not available. An example of such a serialised node model is illustrated in Figure 13, which shows the internal structure of a trained model and highlights how the components of the power function baseline, per-core coefficients, and model type are preserved in a machine-readable form.


```
{
  "model_kind": "gpu",
  "model_type": "linear_free_fit",
  "linear_model": {
    "p_base": 134.0,
    "p_unit": 133.45599999999996,
    "fitted_intercept": 195.28500000000003
  },
  "x_col": "gpu_load",
  "timestamp": "2026-01-20T12:06:20.200692",
  "node_name": "smartcash",
  "source_files": {
    "measurement_run0.csv": 0.25,
    "measurement_run1.csv": 0.5,
    "measurement_run2.csv": 0.75,
    "measurement_run3.csv": 1.0
  },
  "cpu_info": {
    "cores": 12,
    "model": "Xeon Silver 4214 @ 2.20GHz"
  },
  "gpu_info": {
    "count": 1,
    "by_model": {
      "NVIDIA TU104 [GeForce RTX 2080 SUPER]": 1
    }
  },
  "polynomial_model": {
    "a": -125.52000000000001,
    "b": 290.35600000000005,
    "c": 156.06
  }
}
```

Figure 13: Exemplary Node Model stored as JSON.

Our tooling also provides a comparison of fitted linear and polynomial models as illustrated in Figure 14, visualising the improved accuracy and realism achieved by capturing non-linearities in CPU power scaling behaviour. Figure 15 presents a model quality evaluation, for an example node, comparing the prediction accuracy of both the linear and polynomial power models. The results demonstrate that both models exhibit a high degree of accuracy in estimating power consumption across varying CPU load levels. This performance can be attributed to two key factors: first, the models are specifically tailored to the node's CPU characteristics, using empirical measurements collected under controlled stress conditions which already integrate the most important source of power consumption and also contain the consumption of the fans and other smaller energy consuming parts of the node; second, each model incorporates a precisely measured baseline power value, which captures idle consumption and anchors the overall prediction.

By focusing on CPU-centric behaviour, which is typically the dominant contributor to server power consumption in controlled test-bed environments, the models can provide realistic and repeatable estimates. These estimates are well-suited for use in energy-aware experiment planning, system benchmarking, and lifecycle impact analysis. In addition to CPU-centric modelling, the framework has been extended to support accelerator-aware energy modelling for GPU-equipped nodes. GPU power consumption is characterised through controlled stress experiments and integrated into the same regression-based modelling approach, enabling consistent comparison between linear and polynomial models for accelerator-intensive workloads. This extension allows the tooling to capture non-linear GPU power scaling behaviour and to account for the significant contribution to overall system energy consumption in heterogeneous infrastructures.

Figure 14: Regression Fitting Models of CPU Power Consumption (linear and polynomial).

	filename	cores	avg_power	per_core_power	predicted_linear	error_linear	predicted_poly	error_poly
0	measurement_run00.csv	1	134.07	53.07	141.37	5.45%	136.72	1.97%
1	measurement_run01.csv	2	147.00	33.00	146.61	0.26%	145.06	1.32%
2	measurement_run02.csv	3	154.03	24.34	151.85	1.41%	152.63	0.91%
3	measurement_run03.csv	4	161.35	20.09	157.09	2.64%	159.42	1.20%
4	measurement_run04.csv	5	164.92	16.78	162.33	1.57%	165.44	0.31%
5	measurement_run05.csv	6	169.55	14.76	167.57	1.17%	170.68	0.67%
6	measurement_run06.csv	7	173.58	13.23	172.81	0.44%	175.14	0.90%
7	measurement_run07.csv	8	178.17	12.15	178.05	0.06%	178.83	0.37%
8	measurement_run08.csv	9	181.80	11.20	183.29	0.82%	181.74	0.03%
9	measurement_run09.csv	10	185.07	10.41	188.53	1.87%	183.88	0.64%

Figure 15: Prediction Accuracy of Linear vs. Polynomial Prediction Models.

5.4.1 Modeling and Prediction for Virtualized Deployments

The model can describe and predict power consumption of experiments running within virtual machines. We express the power consumption of the physical server as the sum of a baseline idle component and the aggregated resource usage of all hosted virtual machines. Rather than treating virtual machines as independent power consumers, the model distributes host-level power to VMs proportionally according to their utilisation of shared resources.

$$P_{\text{server}} = \sum P_{\text{VM}_i}$$

For each virtual machine, power consumption is estimated as the weighted contribution of CPU, GPU, and NIC resources, derived from the corresponding host-level energy models. CPU-related power is attributed to individual VMs using a fractional allocation factor, representing the proportion of active host CPU resources consumed by the VM during the experiment. This fraction is derived from VM configuration and runtime metadata (e.g. number of virtual CPUs and observed load).

$$P_{\text{VM}_i} = \frac{P_{\text{base}}}{n} + \sum_{i=1}^{n_c} \lambda_i \cdot P_{\text{core},i} + \sum_{j=1}^{n_g} \lambda_j \cdot P_{\text{gpu},j} + \sum_{k=1}^{n_n} a_k \cdot P_{\text{nic},k}$$

The measured idle baseline power of the host system is distributed evenly across all active virtual machines, reflecting the shared cost of maintaining the underlying physical infrastructure. This prevents double-counting of idle power while ensuring that each VM is assigned an equal share of baseline consumption.

Network-related power consumption is attributed based on the association between virtual network interfaces and physical NIC activity, enabling VM-level estimation of network-induced energy usage. For GPU-equipped hosts, the power can be incorporated analogously by allocating GPU power contributions to VMs utilizing GPU passthrough.

This extension allows the existing component-based power model to be applied to virtualized workloads without requiring additional physical instrumentation. By combining host-level energy models with structured VM allocation metadata, the tooling enables reproducible and comparable energy estimation for experiments running in virtual machines, thereby extending its applicability to cloud-like and multi-tenant testbed environments.

5.4.2 Modeling and Prediction for High-Performance Computation

The model is applicable to high-performance computing workloads, which are characterized by multi-node distributed workflows. High-performance computing (HPC) workloads are typically characterised by distributed execution across multiple compute nodes, often combining CPU-, GPU-, and network-intensive tasks. To support energy estimation for such scenarios, the modelling framework extends naturally from single-node prediction to system-wide aggregation across multiple nodes.

In this context, total system power consumption is expressed as the sum of the predicted power contributions of all participating servers or nodes. Each node is modelled independently using the previously described component-based power model, accounting for baseline consumption as well as additive contributions from CPU, GPU, and NIC activity. The resulting per-node predictions are then aggregated to derive the overall power demand of the distributed workload.

Formally, the total predicted power of a distributed experiment is computed as:

$$P_{\text{system}} = \sum P_{\text{server}}$$

where P_{server} denotes the predicted power consumption of each participating server, derived from its individual configuration and load parameters.

This additive aggregation reflects the structure of typical HPC and testbed workflows, where nodes operate largely independently while contributing collectively to overall system energy consumption. By preserving node-level separation, the approach enables detailed analysis of how individual node configurations and roles contribute to total power demand, supporting identification of energy hotspots and imbalanced resource usage within distributed experiments.

The prediction tooling directly supports this system-wide aggregation through its interactive interface. Users can configure load parameters for multiple nodes simultaneously and obtain a combined power prediction that visualises the cumulative contribution of all nodes, disaggregated by CPU, GPU, and NIC components. Figure 17 illustrates an example of such a multi-node prediction, where individual node contributions are stacked to form a unified system-level power estimate.

This modelling approach is particularly well-suited for energy-aware planning of high-performance and large-scale experiments, as it allows researchers to explore the energy implications of scaling workloads across nodes without requiring access to the full physical infrastructure. By combining

reproducible node-level models with straightforward aggregation, the framework enables consistent and transparent energy estimation for distributed and HPC-style workloads.

5.5 Interactive Prediction and Exploration

To make energy awareness an integral part of experiment planning, a browser-based interactive prediction interface has been developed using Jupyter²⁷ and the ipywidgets library²⁸. This tool allows researchers to simulate and visualise the expected energy consumption of an experiment before its execution, thereby supporting energy-conscious design decisions at early stages of the workflow.

The interface exposes a configurable set of parameters that reflect realistic system setups. Users can select predefined CPU load levels (*Idle, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100%*) as well as specify the number of active CPU cores per node. For GPU-equipped nodes, the interface additionally allows users to configure GPU utilisation levels (0–100%) based on available accelerator models. In parallel, NICs can be toggled on or off based on the energy prediction needed for a specific experiment. The interface includes convenience buttons to activate or deactivate all load levels and NICs. GPU configuration controls are dynamically enabled only when a corresponding GPU energy model is available for the selected node. For improved usability, hovering over NIC buttons reveals full model identifiers via tooltips, aiding in hardware-specific analysis. The output is presented as stacked bar charts that disaggregate predicted power consumption into CPU, GPU and NIC contributions, shown in blue and green respectively with GPU contributions visualised as an additional stacked component. These charts enable an immediate visual comparison of different hardware configurations and load conditions.

Figure 16 shows the prediction output for a single node, where the energy consumption increases with CPU load, and the impact of enabled NICs is reflected in the additional green bars. The chart illustrates how even moderate increases in core activity can lead to non-trivial changes in power usage. Figure 17 extends this concept to combined multi-node predictions, aggregating estimated power drawn from multiple nodes into a unified system-wide prediction. Each node's CPU, GPU and NIC contributions are clearly separated, allowing researchers to identify energy bottlenecks and understand how individual node configurations contribute to total system consumption. This interactive tool is particularly useful during experimental design phases. It allows users to assess the energy implications of various configurations without requiring access to physical hardware or prior measurements, provided that a suitable power model has been trained. It also supports scenario testing for sustainability reporting and helps guiding researchers toward energy-efficient setups and experiments.

²⁷ <https://jupyter.org>

²⁸ <https://ipywidgets.readthedocs.io/>

Node Selection

elva narva rīga **smartcash** tapa

Smartcash Configuration

CPU: Xeon Silver 4214 @ 2.20GHz

GPU: NVIDIA TU104 [GeForce RTX 2080 SUPER]

Select CPU Load Level

Idle (0%) **25% Load** 50% Load 75% Load 100% Load

Select GPU Load Level

Idle (0%) 25% Load 50% Load **75% Load** 100% Load

Select NICs

Intel 10-Gigabit X... **82579LM Gigabit** Intel E810-XXV

Select Number of Cores

Cores: 12

Figure 16: Interactive Power Consumption Prediction Widget for One Node.

Figure 17: Interactive Power Consumption Total System Power Prediction for Multiple Nodes.

5.6 Impact on Researcher Behaviour

The tooling developed in Task 5.2 makes a substantial contribution toward embedding energy awareness in experimental design and execution. By combining empirical energy measurements with predictive modelling, the system equips researchers with practical insights into the energy cost of their experiments and hardware choices. In particular, it highlights the energy implications of different load levels and the total system energy consumption. These capabilities promote more sustainable system configurations and encourage energy-aware decision-making from the outset of the experimental workflow.

Aligned with the broader objectives of the GreenDIGIT project, this tooling assists researchers in assessing and minimising the environmental impact of their computational work. It delivers open and extensible interfaces for reproducible energy assessment and supports the full lifecycle evaluation of research workflows. In doing so, it directly contributes to Work Package 5 by enabling optimised software and system design, and to Work Package 6 by providing structured energy consumption data as input for carbon footprint calculation and emissions reporting.

Ultimately, the system prepares experimental testbeds for a future in which experimenting, reproducibility, and sustainability are tightly coupled. It transforms energy measurement from a post-hoc consideration into an integral part of experimental planning, analysis, and communication thereby fostering more responsible and transparent research practices across disciplines.

6 Managing, analysing, and sharing end-to-end energy and sustainability metrics

To conduct the LCA of their experiments, users of RIs need to collect a set of data regarding such experiments. A large part of the environmental impact of experiments is caused by the execution stage, through the energy consumption of the RI running such experiments. Developers must thus collect the amount of energy used by their experiments, as well as the environmental impact of generating such energy.

Collecting such information is possible with the help of energy probes, and environmental data collected by RI operators. While existing tools allow for accessing energy and environmental data, the challenge rather lies in the management of such data, in particular when the detailed results must be shared as open data.

6.1 Context and challenges

6.1.1 Conventional infrastructures

Existing software probes allow for instance to monitor the different processes or virtual machines on a server (Scaphandre, PowerAPI, Kepler), to monitor snippets of code (PyJoule, JJoule). Such probes can be deployed by users of RIs if they have sufficient privileges on the resource they use. However, such probes can only be deployed on standard servers or laptops. They cannot be deployed to other devices, such as IoT things or network appliances. Hardware probes are more flexible with regards to the type of devices they support. However, hardware probes must be deployed by the operator of the RI, their availability is thus a design decision of RI operators.

The coexistence of hardware and software probes, monitoring different scopes of an infrastructure, allows for collecting multi-granularity data. For instance, a PoE-powered IoT infrastructure may be monitored synchronously with software probes for each process of each device, with hardware probes on the PoE switch monitoring the overall energy consumption of each device, and with a larger-scale probe monitoring the total energy consumption of the PoE switch itself.

While this allows for both large-scale and detailed analysis, it also introduces some complexity in data management. In particular, the same energy is accounted for in the different layers of granularity, making data aggregation error-prone, in particular when the granularity levels and the number of monitored nodes increase.

In addition, in such large infrastructure, the different nodes running a given experiment may be located in different regions and thus powered by electricity grid with different environmental impacts. Calculating the environmental impact of such software requires detailed knowledge of the exact energy consumption of each node, its location, and the environmental impact of electricity, in such locations, at the time the software is running.

6.1.2 End-to-end assessments and non-conventional RIs: IoT, Networking, end-users

Existing tools largely focus on server infrastructures by monitoring energy at the PSU level or the CPU level, or more recently the GPU level. While this paradigm allows for monitoring a large part of data centre energy consumption, it does not cover the complete infrastructure. Transversal resources such as the networking devices or storage nodes are usually not monitored. In addition, this approach is not currently adapted to IoT infrastructures, due to the large number of heterogeneous devices, relying on non-conventional network infrastructures such as Wi-Fi or LoRa. For instance, SLICES 6G blueprints rely on antennas. Their energy consumption must be monitored to correctly assess the energy use of experiments relying on this blueprint.

The things-to-cloud continuum is a worst-case scenario of such limitations. The things-to-cloud continuum refers to the seamless integration of physical devices ("things" of the Internet of Things (IoT)) and cloud computing resources. It encompasses all intermediate layers, such as edge and fog computing, allowing data processing and decision-making to occur across a spectrum from the device level to the cloud. The things-to-cloud continuum thus relies on many resources: the IoT layer can be composed of many Things, edge nodes, and cloud nodes. Each of these layers relies on a supporting network.

In this scenario, monitoring remains possible by deploying the relevant probes on all components of the infrastructure. However, this operation will produce many energy data, formatted as time series. On the one hand, aggregating all energy consumption as the sum of the different time-series would provide a coarse-grained result. On the other hand, keeping track of the association between time-series and probes, between probes and the hardware they monitor, and between the monitored devices and their responsibility in the infrastructure remains a challenge, due to the amount of data.

In the use-case of energy efficiency of RI, the ability to share results of energy-related experiments is primordial. Such data can be used to validate the results of research projects, e.g. to demonstrate performance gains, but also used by future workers needing larger datasets of real-world data.

6.2 Metadata model of the environmental impact of experiments

The proposed solution to such challenges is to provide a tool for developers to handle the amount of data generated during end-to-end energy measurement. The proposed solution is to specify a meta-data model to describe the collected energy metrics, to provide a tool to create such meta-data in parallel to the instrumentation of experiment. A running example of the meta-data creation is provided on a use-case.

An experiment can thus be modelled as a tree, with each monitored device as nodes. The root of such a tree is the overall energy consumption of the experiment, while the leaves are the finest granularity of each monitored component. Such a tree can be completed with abstract nodes, allowing the user to represent the energy consumption of a given scope of the experiment without measuring this scope.

A single node can be monitored with several probes, in order to compare such probes or to validate models of energy consumption. Therefore, the model supports the co-existence of several probes for a given node.

The purpose of such metadata is to study the environmental impact of a given experiment. Energy consumption reporting is not sufficient for such a goal, as the environmental impact of each node may be altered by context external to the experiment. In particular, the location of the node and the time of the experiment can affect the electricity mix used by the RI. Therefore, the metadata model supports the inclusion of sustainability metrics. For a given node, a set of metrics can be defined, quantifying the environmental impact of producing the electricity in different categories of impact with their respective unit. Such metrics are node-specific, as different nodes can be in different physical location and thus relying on different electricity mix. The list of metrics is user-defined to adapt to the needs of users and to the metrics available in each RI.

Figure 18 presents the data model of such metadata, with the Node class and its children modelling the tree, the Probe class modelling the probes of each node, and the SustainabilityMetrics class specifying the node-specific set of metrics for the environmental impact of electricity.

Figure 18: Data model for the energy metadata.

6.3 Application to a Things-to-cloud continuum use-case

The purpose of this metadata model is to keep track of the environmental impact of a given experiment as a coarse-grain indicator, while retaining finer granularity to explain such impact at a per-device or per-process granularity. IoT experiment can be considered as a worst-case scenario in terms of the amount of hardware involved and the heterogeneity of such hardware. In addition, measuring end-to-end impacts imposes to monitor resources that may be on different sites, while including support infrastructures such as the network or cooling system.

Figure 19 presents a possible tree modelling the monitoring of such an experiment. Each node of the tree refers to a given monitoring scope. In this experiment, all hardware components, i.e., the IoT devices, the edge and cloud servers, and the network devices, are monitored with hardware probes.

In addition, software probes are deployed on the edge and cloud server to monitor the internal estimated energy consumption of each Virtual Machine they host. Software and hardware probes produce a distinct time-series of energy consumption. In addition, the tree declares abstract nodes, to create clusters of nodes that can be analysed as a group, i.e., the cluster of IoT devices, the clusters of VMs running either on the edge or cloud servers, or the cluster of network infrastructures. Finally, as the metadata model supports several probes on a given node, this model remains relevant in scenarios where the purpose of the experiment is to compare the accuracy of different energy probes, or to validate the energy consumption estimated by a software or modelled probe against a ground truth provided by hardware probes. While the meta-data allows for analysing and sharing the environmental impact of a given experiment, it can also be used to compare experiments. For instance, in the domain of IoT and of the things-to-cloud continuum, there is an interest in identifying the most sustainable architecture for an infrastructure.

Figure 19: Monitored resources during an experiment and a tree modelling such resources.

As shown in Figure 20, the meta-data model allows for comparing both the overall environmental impact of different scenarios, but also to delve into the environmental impact of each node of the tree for further analysis. In particular, the abstract node modelling sub-parts of the infrastructure allows for easily comparing different scopes of the infrastructure despite potential differences across scenarios, e.g., in Figure 20, scenario 2 has more IoT devices than scenario 1.

Figure 20: Multi-granularity, cross-scenario analyses of environmental impact in a potential IoT use-case.

7 Prototype Components

This work package introduces a collection of methodologies and open-source tools to assist RI users in assessing the energy consumption and environmental impact of their experiments. While such tools can be used as standalone, they also complement each other to build a tool chain for assessing, analysing and sharing the end-to-end environmental impact of their experiment.

7.1 Implementation of CIM as an API for RI Integration

The CIM proposed in Section 4 lends itself naturally to implementation as a modular, standards-compliant RESTful API. This API layer would expose core functionalities of the system, such as metric ingestion, classification, namespace generation, semantic packaging, and metadata querying to external components, services, and RIs.

By abstracting the ingestion and semantic mapping logic behind a unified API, the CIM becomes infrastructure-agnostic, capable of integrating seamlessly into diverse research environments. RIs can submit metric data directly through API endpoints (e.g., `/ingest`, `/parse`, `/classify`), retrieve unified keys (`/namespace/unified_key?raw=cpu_usage`), or fetch associated JSON-LD metadata blocks (`/metadata/unified_key`). The API could also allow external tools to query the internal taxonomy (categories, subcategories, standard mappings) or contribute new metric definitions via authenticated POST requests, enabling collaborative extensibility.

This implementation model supports integration with automated monitoring agents, RO-Crate generators, workflow engines, or even FAIR data repositories, making the CIM a versatile node within the broader research ecosystem. With support for both batch and real-time communication, and alignment with OpenAPI or JSON Schema definitions, this API can form the semantic backbone of next-generation sustainable and interoperable RIs. The code for the GreenDIGIT CIM is available publicly online²⁹.

Currently the Impact Assessment Dashboard (specified D5.1) partially implements the CIM specifications. Session reading metrics and the RO-Crate metadata standard is currently in-place, along with other metadata content. However, more iterations and development must be pursued for a more robust and well-rounded tool to be provided. This involves further iteration development cycles and refinement for validation of the current use-case—theoretical background was already established to better allow for this further development.

²⁹ <https://github.com/g-uva/GreenDIGIT-CIM/>

7.2 Jupyter-based Environmental Impact Assessment Tool for Testbed Experiment

The Jupyter-based environmental impact assessment tool was described in Chapter 5. While it is currently operated on SLICES-RI Post-5G Blueprint Infrastructure, it was designed with portability in mind. It requires Jupyter notebooks which are already available on all GreenDIGIT RIs and additional Python packages, e.g. for plotting. A more detailed explanation of the usage of Jupyter notebooks can be found in D5.1. Besides SLICES-RI-specific energy interfaces, Prometheus energy data feeds can be selected as data sources. Prometheus is an industry standard metric collection application and is used in all GreenDIGIT RIs, allowing the tool to be ported with minor adaptations to other environments.

The code of the tool is available online publicly³⁰.

It requires Jupyter notebooks and then additional Python libraries pandas, matplotlib, and seaborn.

There are four Jupyter notebook files in total which are described as follows.

7.2.1 `evaluation.ipynb` — Energy Data Visualisation

The Jupyter-based environmental impact assessment tool analyses energy data from CSV files in the `energy/` folder and metadata from `ro-crate-metadata.json`. It generates visualisations like power trends, cumulative energy, energy rate (mW/s), power vs. CPU load (if available), current/voltage trends, and per-node energy bar charts. It also provides metadata summaries and clickable topology links. Using Jupyter notebooks and Python libraries (pandas, matplotlib, seaborn), it ensures portability and compatibility with Prometheus and SLICES-RI data sources, producing interactive plots and tables.

This notebook analyses raw energy CSV files for multiple nodes and runs.

- Loads and processes CSV energy data dynamically.
- Extracts node-level metadata from `ro-crate-metadata.json`.
- Provides in-depth visualisations:
 - Power over time
 - Cumulative energy usage
 - Energy rate (mW/s)
 - Power vs. CPU load (if CPU data available)

³⁰<https://gitfront.io/r/kili-w/oR4EM3HRV4Kz/green-digit/>

- Current and voltage trends
- Per-node energy bar charts
- Generates formatted metadata summaries and clickable topology links.

Input: energy/ folder & ro-crate-metadata.json Output: Visual plots + metadata tables

7.2.2 energy_model.ipynb — CPU Energy Modeling

The model fitting tool analyses CPU-only energy data from stress test runs. It fits linear (with or without idle intercept) and quadratic polynomial models, saving each as a `cpu_model_<node>.json` file in the `data/cpu_models/` directory for future predictions. Built with Jupyter notebooks and Python libraries (pandas, matplotlib, seaborn), it integrates with Prometheus and SLICES-RI data sources, ensuring portability and robust energy analysis.

This notebook performs regression modelling (linear/polynomial) to stress test results.

- Uses stress-run outputs from previous testbed executions.
- Fits two model types:
 - Linear (with or without idle intercept)
 - Polynomial (quadratic)
- Stores each trained model as a `.json` file for later prediction.

Input: CPU-only energy runs (per node) Output: Model file `cpu_model_<node>.json` stored in `data/cpu_models/`

7.2.3 prediction.ipynb — Interactive Power Prediction

The server power prediction tool forecasts power draw for servers using models and user-defined configurations. Users can select multiple nodes to predict total or individual power consumption. For each node, users specify active NICs, the number of active CPU cores, and target CPU load (0–100%). The tool provides interactive visualisations, including per-node stacked plots and system-wide stacked summaries, updating live as inputs change. Built with Jupyter notebooks and Python libraries (pandas, matplotlib, seaborn), it integrates with Prometheus and SLICES-RI data sources for portability and accuracy.

This notebook predicts server power draw using trained models and user-defined configurations.

- Select multiple nodes to simulate total or individual power draw.
- For each node:
 - Choose active NICs

- Set number of active CPU cores
- Select target CPU load (0–100%)
- Visual prediction modes:
 - Per-node stacked plots
 - System-wide stacked summary
- Fully interactive and updates live on input change.

Input : CPU model files (cpu_model_<node>.json)

Output: Live power prediction visualisations

7.2.4 `api_integration.ipynb` — Publish RO-Crates to GreenDIGIT Catalogue

The RO-Crate metadata extraction and publishing tool streamlines the process of sharing research data. It extracts key metadata, including title, description, keywords, and authors, from the `ro-crate-metadata.json` file in a local RO-Crate folder. The tool prompts users to upload the sipped RO-Crate and provide the public link. It then constructs a metadata entry `package_create` function and submits it to the GreenDIGIT catalogue. Upon successful submission, the tool automatically detects and displays the final dataset URL in the catalogue. Built with Jupyter notebooks and Python libraries (pandas, matplotlib, seaborn), it ensures compatibility with Prometheus and SLICES-RI data sources for seamless integration and portability.

This notebook extracts metadata from a local RO-Crate and publishes it to the GreenDIGIT catalogue using the gCat API.

- Extracts title, description, keywords, and authors from `ro-crate-metadata.json`
- Prompts users to upload the zipped RO-Crate to their D4Science Workspace and input the public link
- Builds and submits a `package_create`-compatible metadata entry
- Automatically detects and prints the final dataset URL in the catalogue

Input: RO-Crate folder (e.g., `./result_folder_examples/...`)

Output: Published dataset visible online³¹.

³¹<https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/GreenDIGIT/>

7.3 Python environmental metadata package

In Section 6, a tool was introduced to structure environmental and energy metadata for analysing and sharing. Creating the meta-data file describing the environmental impact of an experiment is an additional workload for the user of RIs. This workload may affect the adoption of the practice of creating and sharing such data. To tackle this limitation, the creation of such data must be streamlined with the instrumentation of the experiment itself.

To automate such a process, researchers rely on one or several scripts executing the different steps of the process. While such scripts can be created in any programming language, Python is widely adopted for experimental research, either as standalone solutions, or within frameworks such as Jupyter Lab. Therefore, a tool is proposed to programmatically create environmental metadata in parallel to the instrumentation of the experiment, within the instrumentation scripts themselves

The tool is implemented as an open-source Python package. The tool proposes a collection of features to create the meta-data file:

- **Declaring the topology of the tree.** Each node of the tree can be declared in parallel to the reservation of the resource that this node represents.
- **Declaring the probes associated with each node.** Each node can be monitored with one or many software or hardware probes or models, to allow comparison and validation of such probes and models.
- **Declaring the selected categories of environmental impact.** Each node can be associated with a set of environmental intensity of the electricity mix in different user-defined categories of environmental impact.
- **Importing and exporting meta-data files.** Serialising the meta-data in a file allows for integrating it to the open data of the experiment. The shared meta-data can then be deserialised for automated analysis by the experimenter but also the reviewers or future users of the open data. The data is serialised in the JSON format.

Figure 21: Metadata creation workflow with the Python package.

Figure 21 illustrates the workflow of creating energy metadata from the point of view of a user. All interactions with the energy metadata Python package are performed dynamically from within the script instrumenting the experiment. The topology of the tree is declared dynamically based on resource reservations confirmed by the RI. Binding probes to nodes is performed based on the specific probes available on such resources. The energy usage of each probe and the associated environmental data are collected as historical data once the experiment is performed and associated with the relevant nodes and probes. The metadata can then be exported as JSON for integration into the open data. An example of such a JSON file is provided in Appendix C. The usage of this package is simplified to a class serving as a facade, allowing developers to interact with the metadata tree through a single object, as visible in the code snippet below.


```
tree = tree()
tree.add_node("root", "compute", "compute")
tree.add_node("root", "sensors", "sensors")
tree.add_node("sensors", "sensor2_1", "child 2 1")
tree.add_node("sensors", "sensor2_2", "child 2 2")
tree.add_node('compute', "core_package", "core package")
tree.add_node("core_package", "compute1_1", "core 0")
tree.add_node("core_package", "compute1_2", "core 1")

tree.find_node("core_package").add_probe(probe("rap1",0.5,"uj", type="measured",
data_type="csv", path="./export_package.csv"))
tree.find_node("compute1_1").add_probe(probe("rap1", 0.5,"uj", type="measured",
data_type="csv", path="./export_core0.csv"))
tree.find_node("compute1_2").add_probe(probe("rap1", 0.5,"uj", type="measured",
data_type="csv", path="./export_core1.csv"))

tree.export_tree_to_json()
```

The current implementation of the tool is available on a public Git repository³², and open to further evolution based on the needs of RI users and future developments of the GreenDIGIT project.

7.4 Continuation of Task T5.2 Outcomes

The outcomes of Task T5.2 are reused as input to several other tasks. The CIM is destined to be a core component of the environmental metrics publication system, developed in Task T6.1. Again, Task T6.1 lays the foundation for several other research activities. The metrics are input for the energy-aware brokering logic for scientific workflows (Task T6.3). Task T6.3 applies the previously developed energy model, prediction model, framework, and tools, expressing the energy behavior of GPU, AI, VM, and multi-node (HPC) workloads which will be input to the constraint logic solver. Task T7.2 is a consumer of Task T6.1.

Task T6.2 works on modelling of IoT resources. Our Python framework laid a foundation to unite various consumption measurement and estimation sources into a holistic overview.

Our work on reproducible workflows, data formats, and automated publishing will be continued in Task T7.3, which will prototype a Reproducibility as a Service (Raas) platform.

³²https://gitlab.com/greenspector/energy_metadata_python

8 Conclusion

The presented GreenDIGIT Deliverable D5.2 introduces methodological approaches and tools that advance the ability for RI users to predict, monitor, and share the energy consumption and environmental impact of their experiments running on DRIs.

The methodological approach for assessing the environmental impact of experiments is introduced in Chapter 3. It relies on LCA methodology and ISO 14000, and accounts for both the energy usage of the experiments and the impacts of producing this energy, and a share of the embodied impact of the RI itself imputed to experiments.

To assist RI users in conducting such an assessment, three tools are delivered. Chapter 4 introduces a CIM to centralise system-level metrics of RIs, allowing RI users to access metric collected by RI operators, such as energy or water usage, or greenhouse gas emissions. Chapter 5 introduces energy prediction, monitoring, and visualisation tools to better understand energy usage, and to proactively optimise the energy efficiency of future experiments. Finally, chapter 6 introduces a metadata model to manage and share as open data the end-to-end energy usage and environmental impact of complex experiments, such as IoT projects.

Prototype implementation and technical specification of such tools is provided in chapter 7, in anticipation of their deployment to partner RI in future GreenDIGIT work packages, in particular WP6 and WP7. The development and validation of the CMI will be continued as part of activities of T7.2: Metric reporting and validation in RIs. Environmental Impact Metric Assessment tool will be integrated with activities in T7.3: Prototyping platform for Reproducibility as a Service. The validation includes dimensions such as portability to other RIs, application domains, and other workflows. The sustainability metadata tool will be reused in T6.2: Modelling and optimisation of IoT resources and integrate into its monitoring framework.

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Appendix A. Examples of GreenDIGIT Namespace Prefix and URI for Different Metric KPIs

ENERGY METRICS			
Metric Name	URI (Qname) Example	Unit	Description
Total Energy Consumed	gd-metric:energy/totalEnergy	kWh	Total energy used by a system, VM, site, or workflow
Energy Per Task	gd-metric:energy/energyPerTask	kWh/task	Energy associated with execution of a single job
VM Energy Consumption	gd-metric:energy/vmEnergy	Wh	Normalised energy per virtual machine
...
EFFICIENCY METRICS			
Metric Name	URI (Qname) Example	Unit	Description
Power Usage Effectiveness	gd-metric:efficiency/PUE	Ratio	Total facility power / IT power (closer to 1 = more efficient)
Total Usage Effectiveness	gd-metric:efficiency/TUE	Ratio	Total energy / energy used by CPU+memory
PowerScore23 (PS23)	gd-metric:efficiency/PS23	W/HS23	Normalised CPU energy efficiency across sites (TDP/HS23)
...
CARBON EMISSION METRICS			

Metric Name	URI (Qname) Example	Unit	Description
Carbon Usage Effectiveness	gd-metric:carbon/CUE	kgCO ₂ /kWh	Total facility power / IT power (closer to 1 = more efficient)
CO ₂ Emission per Task	gd-metric:carbon/emissionPerTask	gCO ₂ /task	Total energy / energy used by CPU+memory
Carbon Intensity	gd-metric:carbon/carbonIntensity	gCO ₂ /kWh	Emission factor of electricity at a site or region
...
WATER USAGE METRICS			
Metric Name	URI (Qname) Example	Unit	Description
Water Usage Effectiveness	gd-metric:water/WUE	L/kWh	Water used per unit of IT energy
Water per Job	gd-metric:water/waterPerTask	L/task	Estimated water used per task execution
Total Water Consumption	gd-metric:water/totalWater	Litres	Total site water usage (cooling, etc.)
...
RESOURCE UTILISATION METRICS			
Metric Name	URI (Qname) Example	Unit	Description
CPU Utilisation	gd-metric:resource/cpuUtilisation	%	Proportion of time CPU is active
Network Utilisation	gd-metric:resource/networkUtilisation	Mbps	Bandwidth usage
Memory Load	gd-metric:resource/memoryUsage	%	RAM used vs total available

...
-----	-----	-----	-----

Appendix B. Example of a JSON-LD for Power Usage Metric Instance in CIM Context

```
{
  "@context": {
    "gd-metric": "https://w3id.org/greendigit/metrics#",
    "iso30134": "https://w3id.org/iso30134#",
    "dc": "http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/",
    "prov": "http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#",
    "unit": "http://qudt.org/vocab/unit#",
    "xsd": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#"
  },
  "@id": "urn:uuid:a8e14b6a-9d43-4bcd-845d-c47e4c5171f9",
  "@type": "gd-metric:EnergyObservation",
  "iso30134:avgPower": {
    "@value": 238.4,
    "@type": "xsd:float",
    "unit:hasUnit": "unit:W"
  },
  "dc:source": "DataCenter-A",
  "dc:timestamp": "2025-05-01T10:42:00Z",
  "gd-metric:classifiedAs": "gd-metric:iso30134/energy/avgPower",
  "gd-metric:rawKey": "dc_power",
  "gd-metric:aliases": ["powerUsed", "powerConsumption"],
  "prov:wasDerivedFrom": {
    "@id": "urn:uuid:raw-datacenter-a-file",
    "dc:format": "application/json",
    "dc:creator": "AWS CloudWatch",
    "dc:title": "Power log snapshot"
  },
  "gd-metric:category": "energy",
  "gd-metric:subcategory": "power",
  "gd-metric:description": "Average power used over a 15-minute window in watts as reported by the facility UPS."
}
```

Detail Description of JSON-LD Components

@context

This section defines namespaces for all the vocabulary prefixes used in the document:

"gd-metric": Custom namespace for our CIM schema.

"iso30134": Refers to the ISO/IEC 30134 standard for datacenter KPIs.

"dc": Dublin Core metadata terms (e.g., source, date, format).

"prov": W3C PROV-O ontology for provenance tracking.

"unit": QUDT ontology for unit declarations.

"xsd": XML Schema Datatypes, used to type values like float, dateTime, etc.

@id

A globally unique identifier (UUID) for this observation. It ensures traceability and reusability in linked datasets.

@type

Specifies the class/type of this metric observation. Here, it's declared as a `gd-metric:EnergyObservation`, linking it to the domain class defined in our schema.

iso30134:avgPower

This is the **actual metric value** being observed, referencing its source standard (ISO 30134).

@value: The observed value (238.4).

@type: The data type of the value (float).

unit:hasUnit: The unit associated with the value, in this case watts (unit:W), using QUDT ontology.

dc:source

Specifies the infrastructure or system that reported the metric—here, "DataCenter-A".

dc:date

The timestamp of the observation in ISO 8601 format, critical for time-series indexing and reproducibility.

gd-metric:classifiedAs

Refers to the fully qualified unified namespace assigned to this metric:

"gd-metric:iso30134/energy/avgPower", indicating standard, category, and metric.

gd-metric:rawKey

The original key as extracted from the source, prior to classification ("dc_power").

This ensures backward compatibility and traceability.

gd-metric:aliases

An array of known synonyms or alternative representations of the raw metric. This enables fuzzy matching, semantic similarity, and enhanced classification.

prov:wasDerivedFrom

Encodes **provenance** information about where and how this observation originated:

@id: Identifier for the original file or API payload.

dc:format: MIME type of the source.

dc:creator: Name of the generating system or tool (e.g., CloudWatch).

dc:title: Human-readable title of the original source file.

gd-metric:category and **gd-metric:subcategory**

These provide hierarchical classification for the metric:

energy (category)

power (subcategory)

gd-metric:description: A plain-language explanation of what the metric measures and how it should be interpreted.

Appendix C. Example of a sustainability metadata JSON file

```
{
  "scope": "root",
  "label": "Root",
  "children": [
    {
      "scope": "client",
      "label": "Client",
      "children": [
        {
          "scope": "device1",
          "label": "Caller",
          "probes": [
            {
              "name": "batterystats",
              "frequency": 0.2,
              "unit": "nAh",
              "type": "measured",
              "data_type": "measured",
              "path": "./device1.csv"
            }
          ]
        },
        {
          "scope": "device2",
          "label": "Callee",
          "probes": [
            {
              "name": "batterystats",
              "frequency": 0.2,
              "unit": "nAh",
              "type": "measured",
              "data_type": "measured",
              "path": "./device2.csv"
            }
          ]
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "scope": "server",
      "label": "Server",
      "probes": [
        {
          "name": "RAPL",
```



```
    "frequency": 1,  
    "unit": "mW",  
    "type": "measured",  
    "data_type": "measured",  
    "path": "./scaphandre.json"  
  }  
],  
"children": [  
  {  
    "scope": "socket",  
    "label": "Socket",  
    "children": [  
      {  
        "scope": "core",  
        "label": "Core"  
      },  
      {  
        "scope": "uncore",  
        "label": "Uncore"  
      },  
      {  
        "scope": "dram",  
        "label": "DRAM"  
      }  
    ]  
  }  
]  
}  
]  
}
```